

SATISFACTORY

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Industrial lab use case Set-up and Demonstration

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AR	Augmented Reality
BSC	Business Scenario
CIDEM	Common Information Data Exchange Model
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EU	European Union
HMI	Human Machine Interface
PDEC	Plant Data Exchange Component
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UWB	Ultra Wide Band
VR	Virtual Reality
WO	Work Order
WP	Work Package
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020), reporting the results of the activities carried out by WP5. SatisFactory aims to develop an ecosystem of innovative technological components that would assist the daily operations of the people working at industrial environment. More specifically the developments of SatisFactory will be demonstrated to three diverse shop floors from discrete manufacturing (COMAU), batch products manufacturing (SUNLIGHT Systems) and continuous processes (CERTH/CPERI). The main focus of the project is around the workers and how to improve their daily activities and increase the collaboration and engagement to the shop floor operations. A user centred approach through an iterative development process with participation of the relevant stakeholders is applied to continuously guide and also validate project developments at the shop floors.

Deliverable D5.3 "Industrial lab use case Set-up and Demonstration" documents the overall context for the deployment of SatisFactory tools and components at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor to exemplify their usage at a pre-industrial level. The activities described in this deliverable are the results of task T5.3 "Deployment of Industry lab use case". Deliverable D5.3 is developed in an iterative approach, so the present document is the first version (M16) of it whereas the second version is due to M24 of the project. The first version focuses on the planning for the implementation of SatisFactory developments at CERTH/CPERI shop floor utilizing the results of D1.2 "Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description" where the needs of the workers and their requirements for a shop floor with enhance operations is described.

Deliverable D5.3 documents the activities that were performed for the analysis of the tools and components of SatisFactory platform at CERTH/CPERI shop floor for the Application Scenarios that cover a wide range of actions involving a multitude of workers with different roles and responsibilities. Finally D1.2 includes a detailed analysis of the status and deployment planning of each components that it is involved at each Business Scenario that are developed to show the functionalities of the SatisFactory platform.

1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a specific description of the roadmap for implementation of each Business Scenario that is determined for CERTH/CPERI shop floor, the status of the tools that are (version 1) or will be (version 2, M24) deployed at the shop floor and the deployment plan for each involved component in order to fulfill the user requirements and needs. The developments of D5.3 cover the activities and procedures that took place at the selected Business Scenarios dealing with Chemical Processes according to the needs of the involved end user (CERTH/CPERI). More specifically the two versions of D5.3 will cover:

- **1st version (M16):** Planning of Scenario realization focusing on deployment/preparation of SatisFactory platform (components, tools, services, interfaces) and installation of infrastructures to the CERTH/CPERI shop-floor.
- **2nd version (M24):** Implementation of the Business Scenarios using the SatisFactory platform and user engagement using all the provided tools from the technology

1.1 *PURPOSE, CONTEXT AND SCOPE OF THIS DELIVERABLE*

The purpose of this deliverable is to give a systematic methodology and a time schedule of the implementation of the Business Scenarios as performed by the selected groups of workers in conjunction with the usage of the appropriate SatisFactory platform components that are necessary in order for the operations to be successfully executed at CERTH/CPERI. The overall activities are guided by the high-level procedures and the use cases as analysed at D1.2 “Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description” in order to address existing issues or barriers related to the knowledge sharing and the collaboration of actors among the various locations at the CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

The roadmap for the implementation activities in this deliverable reflects the work performed in Task T5.3 – “Deployment of Industry lab use case”, with a close collaboration with the activities of Tasks T1.2 – “Models for actors and procedures interconnection” and T1.3 – “Use Cases and Scenarios” where the analysis and definition of the business scenarios, the use cases and the identification of the involved actor groups took place. Also, there is a strong synergy with the activities of Task T5.1 - “SatisFactory Components Integration and Framework”.

The **main objectives** of the activities that were performed at Task T5.3 “Deployment of Industry lab use case” for the 1st version of D5.3 are:

- Definition of the methodology for preparation for implementation of the Business Scenarios and a time schedule for the implementation
- Selection of group of actors to be informed and participate in the preparatory activities
- Set-up and installation of the SatisFactory components and the available tools from the technology partners (until M15) at the CERTH/CPERI industrial shop-floor.
- Setup of the infrastructure for the software related components
- Preliminary tests for validation of the provided functionalities by the tools

- Engaging actors to use the available tools at the shop-floor.
- Develop the appropriate environment to implement parts/sections of the Business Scenarios
- Capture, analyse and communicate end-user needs for the proposed tools in an effective manner.

The developments of Deliverable D5.3 will be continuously updated and refined through an iterative process that will lead to the production of a total of two releases of this document, respectively in Project Months M16 and M24. The development of this deliverable was coordinated by CERTH with contribution of ABE, FIT, ISMB, REGOLA, EPFL and GLASSUP.

1.2 BACKGROUND

The background of the work performed and described in this deliverable is related to the 3rd phase of the project “Prototyping, Implementation and System Integration” and aims at the implementation of the Business Scenarios at CERTH/CPERI shop floor using the tools delivered by the technology providing partners of the project and the engaging of the workers within the activities of the scenarios. Figure 1 shows the relationship between Task T5.3 and the other tasks/WPs in the project.

Figure 1: Activities and Connection of D5.3 with other tasks and WPs

As CERTH/CPERI is the pre-industrial environment most of the SatisFactory components and tools will be initially tested at a small scale using the prototypes which will be built during the project. More specifically, deliverable D5.3 results from activities of WP5 – “Integration, Deployment,

Industrial Trials Demonstration and Evaluation”, which is responsible for the integration and actual implementation of the tools and application environment for a safer and more attractive shop floor to address the need and requirements of the end users at the shop floor. Within WP 5, task T5.3 focuses on the planning and deployment of the SatisFactory developments at CETH/CPERI shop-floor utilizing the components and tools from SatisFactory platform. There exists a strong synergy among deliverable D5.3, derived by the activities of task T5.3, and other tasks in WP5 and other work packages within the project (WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4). Furthermore, inputs from other tasks that run in parallel are required in order to deploy and implement the Business Scenarios (BSCs) that address the needs of the end users at CETH/CPERI, as documented at deliverable D1.1 “User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and deployment guidelines”. The output from this deliverable will be evaluated according to the test described at D5.2 “Evaluation Plan” and will be documented at D5.5 “Final System Evaluation Report”.

This is the first version of the deployment activities which deals mostly with the planning for the deployment and the testing of the components and tools that are available to be used until M15 of the project. The testing and final deployment of the components will be documented at the second version of deliverable D5.3 on M24.

1.3 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

Following this introductory section, the remaining part of the document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 provides a general overview of the approach and methodology for planning of implementation and the context of the CETH/CPERI shop floor where the tools will be implemented.
- Chapter 3 describes the tools that are used at every BSCs which is related to the CETH/CPERI shop floor including their deployment status along with requirements and implementation pre-requisites.
- Chapter 4 includes the planning for the deployment and the initial results from scenario “BSC-5.1 - Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction” that deals with corrective actions that need immediate attention at the various pilot plants at the shop-floor and perform works to repair or replace a faulty or degraded equipment.
- Chapter 5 includes the planning for the deployment and the initial results from scenario “BSC-5.2 - Startup procedures for pilot plants” that deals with the critical start-up procedures of operating hydroprocessing pilot plants using proper Standard Operating Procedures (SOP).
- Chapter 6 includes the planning for the deployment and the initial results from scenario “BSC-5.3 - Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures” that deals with the Improvement of the process workflow for the reconfiguration of a multipurpose unit.
- Chapter 7 includes the planning for the deployment and the initial results from scenario “BSC-6.1 Recognition of incidents and path optimization for workers movement on the shop

floor” that demonstrates the usage of advanced SatisFactory tools to identify incidents at the shop floor related to workers and undesired conditions identified at areas where workers are present targeting the increase of the safety and comfort of the involved actors.

- Finally, Chapter 8 provides general conclusions and guidelines on how the results included in this deliverable will be further elaborated in forthcoming stages of the project activities within the scope of WP5.

This document is supported by one annex that contains the detailed steps of the Standard Operating Procedures with respective photos and connections for two of the scenarios related to CETH/CPERI (BSC-5.1, BSC-5.3).

2 GENERIC APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY FOR PLANNING OF IMPLEMENTATION

The goal of Chapter 2 is to describe the planning methodology towards the deployment of SatisFactory tools at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor in order to realize the scenarios that were derived by the use needs and requirements. The main objective is to enhance and enrich CERTH/CPERI shop-floor environment integrating key enabling technologies such as intelligent decision support systems (iDSS), augmented reality, wearable and ubiquitous computing as well as and customised social communication platforms coupled with experience design and gamification-based techniques for the efficient transfer of knowledge and collaboration among the workers.

The deployed solutions are categorized using hardware and software, simple and/or complex solutions. The use of the respective set of components will be used to realize and optimize the interactive selected procedures that are performed by the group of workers. Overall the activities for the planning and implementation of SatisFactory developments are organized according to the Business Scenarios that are described in detail at D1.2 “Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description”. Table 1 summarizes the list of the SatisFactory high level Business Scenarios that are developed for CERTH/CPERI shop-floor.

Table 1 List of CERTH/CPERI Business Scenarios and Application Scenarios

Business Scenario	Application Scenario	Name
BSC-5	Online supervision of the operation and workforce resources of pilot plants for chemical processes (CERTH)	
	BSC-5.1	Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction
	BSC-5.2	Startup procedures for pilot plants
	BSC-5.3	Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures
BSC-6	Recognition of incidents and path optimization for workers’ movement (CERTH)	
	BSC-6.1	Recognition of incidents and path optimization for workers movement on the shop floor

In brief the needs and requirements at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor and their connection to the scenarios are summarized to:

- Active collaboration between the various groups of actors (BSC-5.1, BSC-5.2, BSC-5.3)
- Sharing of knowledge from the shop floor to the process supervisor and the director that would improve the decision making procedure in terms of time, effort and global view of each unit (BSC-5.1, BSC-5.2)
- Improvement of the planned maintenance actions by acquiring flow diagrams and electrical schematics depending on the unit, involved subsystem or device (BSC-5.1, BSC-5.3)

- Re-adaptation of the production setup of a continuous process unit based on client’s needs and previously used configurations (BSC-5.3)
- Efficient and fast response at unplanned events based on an augmented interface that would derive online in near real-time information depending the specific problem (BSC-5.1)
- Minimize the safety-related incidents which are caused by erroneous human actions (BSC-6.1)

According to the needs and requirements of BSC-5 and BSC-6, the available SatisFactory platform components are initially installed and afterwards used by the involved workers. Therefore, the activities described in the next chapters are related to the analysis of the tools to be used from the SatisFactory platform (by technology providing partners – CERTH/ITI, ABE, ISMB, REGOLA, EPFL, FIT, GLASSUP) that focus on deployment/testing of the tools. Also during T5.3 there is a preliminary engagement of selected actors (both operators and technicians) to test the available functionalities provided by the tools.

2.1 SHOP FLOOR AREA FOR THE DEPLOYMENT OF THE SCENARIOS

CERTH/CPERI shop-floor has a wide range of industrial automation systems and industrial software platforms. The automated systems are used for process control and remote monitoring (SCADA, DCS, PLC based). CERTH/CPERI’s selected shop-floor processes will be used as a test bed for SatisFactory products and solutions. Figure 2 shows the highlighted areas where the scenarios will be deployed focusing in different perspectives and by engaging all the group of workers of CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

Figure 2 Overview of CERTH/CPERI shop floor and designated areas where the business scenarios will be performed

Figure 3: Partial overview of CERTH/CPERI's shop floor and plants

Within SatisFactory project, CERTH/CPERI utilizes its industrial automation infrastructure for the deployment of the integrated Reference Architecture Platform to CERTH/CPERI's process plants where the Industrial Lab cases are deployed. CERTH/CPERI's infrastructure consists of numerous experimental industrial process systems where information is propagated through a network backbone that facilitates data exchange from and to the input/output field of respective units. Each unit has sensors that acquire various signals which are distributed in a wide area and are connected using industrial networks. Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition Systems (SCADA) for chemical and energy production processes are in operation with respective middleware software.

Figure 4: CERTH/CPERI's Monitoring and control HMIs

CERTH/CPERI has developed and supports a wide multi-sensorial network of heterogeneous distributed systems (indicative industrial protocols: CANBus, Profibus, EtherCat, RS485). The monitoring and control is performed in real time and cover actions and events that take place throughout the life cycle of the information, starting from the encoding at the physical layer to the knowledge sharing to the end user. In order to provide a uniform way of communication at the application layer between the various sources and sinks of data, OPC-based interfaces are developed and deployed at each individual process unit.

2.2 PLANNING OF IMPLEMENTATION

In order to deploy SatisFactory solutions to CERTH/CPERI shop-floor there are a list of activities that need to take place in order to be compliant with the industrial-grade specifications for using new

tools at the shop-floor. The following is a summary of the implementation process, which is followed by CERTH/CPERI personnel in collaboration with the technology providing partners of SatisFactory consortium. CERTH/CPERI team:

- ensures that the design objectives and intent are clearly documented.
- performs a focused review of design specifications of the tools to be used.
- CERTH/CPERI personnel develop an Implementation Plan.
- conducts various scoping meetings where the implementation process is reviewed with the technology providing partners and schedules additional meetings, as necessary, throughout set-up, to plan, coordinate, and schedule future activities and resolve deployment problems.
- works with the technology providing partners in developing start-up plans and start-up documentation formats. The technological partners provide the pre functional checklists to be completed during the startup process.

The technology providing partners execute and document the pre-functional checklists and perform startup and local or remote configuration. CERTH/CPERI team documents that the checklists and startup were completed according to the approved plans. This may include the engaging of actors from the shop-floor besides the development CERTH/CPERI team. In general, performance verification proceeds from simple to complex, from component level to tools and integrated bundled tools, with pre-functional checklists being completed before functional testing. Tools and software documentation is submitted to the CERTH/CPERI team during normal submittals, including detailed set-up procedures.

2.2.1 Methodology for Planning and Stages

The purpose of D5.3 is to define the process to be followed in the delivery and handover of SatisFactory systems and components into operation at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor. This section describes the elements that are considered towards commencement of the tools and components that will be utilized by the workers to implement their daily activities in an improved manner and in active collaboration with the other actors within the shop-floor. The key stages towards implementation are identified along with the order in which these shall be addressed. The key stages are defined below as:

- Stage 1 Design of components – Preparatory actions (Factory Acceptance Tests)
- Stage 2 Set-up at the shop floor (Site Acceptance Testing)
- Stage 3 Deployment and Commissioning
- Stage 4 Operation and Maintenance

Each stage of the implementation process includes a list of actions that need to be in place before the next stage of the process is commenced. At the next sections a specific timeframe for the realization of the aforementioned stages is delivered. As SatisFactory project is related to innovation actions a minor deviation from the exact schedule is anticipated and the finally realized stages will be documented at the 2nd version of this deliverable. Also since the implementation involves workers and the modification of their daily activities, a careful approach to manage the resistance to change is necessary.

2.2.2 Activities and aspects addressed for the Implementation

Towards the deployment for operation of the SatisFactory platform the following activities were performed by the involved technological partners in collaboration with the CErTH/CPeRI team. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to give examples of the requirements on a typical scheme. The following aspects are addressed by the implementation team:

- Coordinate and direct the implementation activities in a logical, sequential and efficient manner using consistent protocols and forms, centralized documentation and clear and regular communications and consultations with all necessary partners.
- Ensure that the design objectives and intent are clearly documented and carried out in the design and set-up stages.
- Develop clear deployment specifications and the functional testing requirements included in the delivered documents.
- Before startup, gather and review the current sequences/operations.
- Approve pre functional tests by reviewing pre functional checklist reports or by direct site observation.
- Coordinate, witness, and approve functional performance tests performed by installing contractors.
- Coordinate re-testing as necessary until satisfactory performance is achieved.
- Oversee and approve the training of the operating workers.
- Provide a final implementation report, which shall include:
 - a. An executive summary, list of participants and roles, brief shop-floor area description, overview of implementation and testing scope, and a general description of testing and verification methods.
 - b. For each components or bundles of components, the report will contain documentation and training meetings in the following areas:
 - 1) Satisfactory components shop-floor specific specifications,
 - 2) Satisfactory components installation,
 - 3) Functional performance and efficiency,
 - 4) Satisfactory components documentation context of use, and
 - 5) Operator training.All outstanding non-compliance items shall be specifically listed.
 - c. Recommendations for improvement, future actions, process changes, etc. will also be listed. Each non-compliance issue shall be referenced to the specific functional test, inspection, etc. where the deficiency is documented.
 - d. The functional performance and efficiency section for each piece of equipment, shall include a brief description of the verification method used including observations and conclusions from the feedback obtained by the involved actors.

During the setup and deployment stages the CErTH/CPeRI team assisted with problem-solving or resolving non-conformance or deficiencies, but ultimately that responsibility resided with the technology providing partner. After notice to proceed from the CErTH/CPeRI team, the up-to-date schedule is at the responsibility of the technology providing partners. The primary role of the planning is to develop and coordinate the execution of a testing plan and observe and document performance, that is, determined whether SatisFactory components/tools are in accordance with their functionalities described at deliverable D2.1 to fulfill the needs documents at deliverable D1.1

and implement the scenarios of deliverable D1.2. The evaluation scenarios and evaluation tests are detailed described at deliverable D5.2.

2.2.3 Time scheduling for each Business Scenario of CERTH/CPERI

An overview of the implementation of the Business Scenarios at the shop-floor is depicted at Figure 5. Since there are many components and tools involved at each scenario the phases are based on the latest delivered tool and each stage starts when at least one of the components are available for design, setup, deployment or operation. Therefore, the actual operation of each scenario is performed gradually. The engaging of the actors will be also performed gradually, initially targeting at a small group and afterwards the selected involved actors will participate, as the tools will be integrated at their daily activities.

At the 1st version of D5.3 the activities related to the implementation and initial testing are included, whereas the entire integrated scenario operation will be documented at the 2nd version of D5.3 due to M24. Thus, the Gantt chart covers only the activities performed until M20 which will be revisited for the components that are not available for deployment at this phase of the project. The preliminary schedule is initially prepared with the knowledge that specific dates will change as deployment and the business scenarios are further progressed. The tools that have entered the operation phase will continue to be evaluated since the installation at the pre-pilot shop floor is their first version. The final version of the components will be setup at the industrial partners.

Figure 5 Gantt diagram of the implementation phases of the Business scenarios at CETH/CPERI

SatisFactory components are documented at deliverable D2.1.2 “SatisFactory System Architecture”. To visualize which components are used for the realization of each scenario the architecture is used as a reference (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Components diagram of the overall SatisFactory architecture

Besides the technical details that covered at deliverable D5.1 “SatisFactory Components Integration and framework” there are various requirements and pre-requisites which is necessary to be covered in order for them to work as designed at the actual working environment which in the case of D5.3 is CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

The hardware related infrastructure that is developed and is dedicated to SatisFactory platform at CERTH/CPERI shop-floor is summarized at Table 2.

Table 2 Dedicated infrastructure at CERTH/CPERI shop floor for SatisFactory platform

Type	Components installed
Server with windows OS (Win 7 pro 64 bits)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> iDSS LinkSmart
Server with Linux OS (Ubuntu 14.04 64 bits)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ontology manager
Server with windows OS (Win 7 pro 32 bits)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC)
Server with windows OS (NUC pc Win 8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gesture and Content Recognition Manager (GCRM)
Raspberry PI mini pc with Linux OS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Localization Devices & Manager
Raspberry PI mini pc with Linux OS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature sensor (Thermal sensor network)

2.3 BUSINESS SCENARIOS AND ARCHITECTURE COMPONENTS

In order to assess the Business Scenarios and their connection with the Satisfactory platform a template was circulated to all partners that includes information related to the component usage, the restrictions/prerequisites and the feasibility of each component to be used at the specific Business Scenario. The purpose of the gathered information is to ensure that the provided components would be able to be adjusted for the scope for the scenarios and to extract a first indication about the priorities and effort/complexity categorization. The provided information considered the context of implementation as described at the specific scenario.

A snapshot of the information that was collected for each component can be seen at Table 3 :

Table 3 Assessment of Business Scenarios and Components

A	B	C	D	E	F
Component name	Direct / Indirect	Effort required	Restrictions	Prerequisites	Feasibility (YES/NO)
Main Component X					
Subcomponent X.Y					

At the first column (A) there are the **categories** of the components and their subcategories. Next at second column (B) there are three options that can be selected from each components subcategory.

- i. Direct: When the Business Scenario uses this component
- ii. Indirect: When the Business Scenario uses this component through another component
- iii. No Usage: When the Business Scenario does not use this component at all

The third column (C) shows how effort required; from scale of 1-3 how difficult is it to incorporate the component to the Business Scenario. The **complexity and effort** which is documented for each component is not related to Person Months (PMs) but to the complexity of integration to the infrastructure of the shop floor. The specific value (1-3) is a measure of prioritization for the technology providing partners and it will assist the evaluation of the implementation aspects of each scenario. The next column (D) relates to the **restrictions** about each components subcategory:

- i. Potential Restrictions, e.g. need to have a specific data format? or size that is read or allowed to be stored?
- ii. Obstacles: language, or feed to specific DB such as Oracle, etc.

The fifth column (E) relates to the **prerequisites** of each components subcategory.

Finally the last column refers to the **feasibility** (YES/NO) of each subcategory. Based on this analysis, the Business Scenarios of the pre-pilot site, CETH/CPERI, were analysed and the technology providing partners evaluated the feasibility of their components to be implemented with respect to the Business Scenarios deployment. The same analyses will be performed for the Business Scenarios of the other two shop floors, Sunlight and COMAU, and will be presented at deliverable D5.4 "Industrial Pilots Set-up and Demonstration".

2.3.1 Business Scenarios and Component Usage

In order to analyse and describe the effect that the components will have to each of the Business Scenarios, a set of diagrams were developed. The following diagram shows the number of components that each Business Scenario of CERTH/CPERI shop floor is using. Each component performs a specific action and can work either as a stand alone or with an interaction with another component.

Figure 7 Number of components for the SatisFactory Business Scenarios at CERTH/CPERI shop floor

2.3.2 Business Scenarios and Components' Implementation Effort

In addition to the above information, there was a need to review the effort that the technological partners will need in order to create the components that they are responsible for. This information is being available at the following diagram.

Figure 8 Component implementation effort per Business Scenario at CERTH/CPERI shop floor

A very important issue that can be mentioned here is that most of the components require effort level 2 in order to be developed.

Figure 9: Summary of “Effort level” needed for the components installed at CERTH/CPERI premises

A summary of “Effort level” needed for the components of SatisFactory can be seen at Figure 9. It is clear that the most of the components require effort level 2 and components that require effort level 1 or 3 are almost the same number. From Figure 9 it is evident that most of the components have normal implementation needs and requirements as defined by the technology providing partner which is a first indication that the business scenarios will be successfully implemented.

2.3.3 Remarks for Implementation and Set-up procedures at CERTH/CPERI

Overall the technology providing partners verified the feasibility for delivering their components and tools at the CERTH/CPERI shop-floor in order to be used to implement the operations and functions described at the scenarios. The status and usage the involved components will be analyzed at a scenarios basis in the following chapters. The information within D5.3 is according to the technical input provided by the partner responsible for the development and delivery of the components/tools. The set-up is performed in close collaboration among the provider and the CERTH/CPERI team, whereas the base infrastructure and the mounting of the equipment at the final position was done by CERTH/CPERI personnel according to the regulations for safety and in compliance with the regulation for commissioning equipment to shop-floors with chemical pilot plants. More specifically the set-up was performed either by local presence or remotely through the appropriate tools for accessing the infrastructures and the servers that are dedicated for SatisFactory project.

3 PLANNING AND DEPLOYMENT OF COMPONENTS USED BY MULTIPLE SCENARIOS

The demonstration of the capabilities and functionalities of SatisFactory platform is verified through the implementation of the aforementioned BSCs that cover the identified needs and requirements of the involved actors at CErTH/CPeRI shop floor. The goal of Chapter 3 is to describe the planning for implementation and the status of the SatisFactory components and tools that are used in multiple scenarios using a common infrastructure. They are described in this chapter in order to avoid repetition of information which is similar to all cases.

As previously mentioned the SatisFactory platform that will be installed at the involved shop floor consists of several components. Some of them are being used at all the Business Scenarios and some of the only at specific Business Scenarios. Therefore, we have two cases about their usage:

- a) To all scenarios or
- b) By the involved workers at the shop floor for activities that are performed to various scenarios.

Table 4 presents the components that are common to all business scenarios and some components that have functionalities that are used by all actors of the shop floor. According to the scenario they provide different functionalities for the end-user at the CErTH/CPeRI shop floor and they are utilized within the context of the procedures performed at each different scenarios. Also as they constitute the basis for the SatisFactory platform (CIDeM, Middleware, etc.) they are parametrically configured to delivered the requested function upon demand. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 4: Identified Components to be utilized in all BSCs at CErTH/CPeRI shop floor

Responsible partner	
CERTH	<p>Component: Repository – Asset Machinery, Production Models</p> <p>Restrictions: All data coming to the Repository from other components must be in xml format, compliant with the B2MML standard</p> <p>Prerequisites: Intranet connection between Repository and the other components</p>
CERTH	<p>Component: Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence</p> <p>Restrictions: Just a visualization of the malfunction and possible of its affects at the process</p> <p>Prerequisites: Formalized operating procedures, and any other available resources</p>
EPFL	<p>Component: Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager</p> <p>Restrictions: Data coming from CIDeM should filter and then loaded within the SCM. A mirror copy of the SF repository is not needed. Every dataset have to be Extracted, Transformed, Loaded (ETL) according to a specific allowed format, for instance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •RDF+XML, RDF+N3, structJSON, structXML, ironJSON, common <p>SCM repository size shouldn't be too big in order not to introduce unhelpful time delay.</p>

	<p>Prerequisites: CIDEM Data have to be available in a format that can be transformed into triplets.</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Suggestions for Improvement platform – “My Factory” – Gamification-based tools Restrictions: The “My Factory” component is to be used via a tablet at a fixed station. It cannot be accessed outside the factory site. Prerequisites: Categories for suggestions are predefined.</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Suggestions for Improvement platform – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools Restrictions: The “My Factory Management” component can only be accessed by the management using their office PCs or laptops. It cannot be accessed outside the factory site. Prerequisites: Categories for suggestions and at least one responsible person for each category is predefined.</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools Restrictions: In order to utilize the gamification framework, each external framework is required to create a game and define the points against each task to be performed by the workers. Prerequisites: The actions related to the external systems that are to be included as tasks in a game are identified beforehand. Rewards, avatars, points and badges are specified beforehand.</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Gamification Framework – “What’s My Score” App – Gamification-based tools Restrictions: The worker can only view his own points. If he desires to view the cumulative team score, he has to view it on the digital screen at the factory site. Prerequisites: For the app to be useful in conveying the current score of the worker, there has to be at least one external system linked to the gamification framework.</p>
ISMB	<p>Component: Middleware – Device Manager Restrictions: Device manager is involved in the case of usage of some environmental data acquisition device. It should be technically possible to integrate involved devices through the device manager Prerequisites: Involved devices API and usage manual availability</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Middleware - Core Services Restrictions: Device Managers and Services are registered into LinkSmart eco-system</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Middleware - Event Manager Restrictions: MQTT protocol is used for publishing and event notification. Message payload is CIDEM compliant Prerequisites: Services needs to learn the designated topics LinkSmart catalogue services, those being configured in a Registration Document by Device Managers</p>
FIT	<p>Component: Middleware - Event Aggregator Restrictions: Store received subscription notifications into CIDEM repository with CIDEM compliant format Prerequisites: CIDEM Repository REST interface is available</p>

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

3.1 REPOSITORY – ASSET MACHINERY, PRODUCTION MODELS

The repository constitutes the basis of the SatisFactory platform. In the Repository, there is a need to store information about the static and the dynamic information that is related to the shop-floor operation, such as physical assets required for the operation of the specific part of the pilot plant, the topology of the overall shop floor, restricted/dangerous areas in it, measurements, events, etc.


```

- <CIDEM>
  - <ShopFloor>
    <ShopFloorID>CPERI</ShopFloorID>
    - <SFInformationModel>
      - <ActorsList>
        - <Actor>
          <b2mml:ID>1</b2mml:ID>
          - <b2mml:Description>
            Overall supervision on the workflow of the shop floor
          </b2mml:Description>
          - <b2mml:Person>
            <b2mml:ID>1</b2mml:ID>
            <b2mml:Description>Managers and Engineers</b2mml:Description>
          </b2mml:Person>
          - <b2mml:PersonnelClass>
            <b2mml:ID>1</b2mml:ID>
            <b2mml:Description>Stakeholders</b2mml:Description>
            - <b2mml:PersonnelClassProperty>
              <b2mml:ID>1</b2mml:ID>
              <b2mml:Description>Floor Manager</b2mml:Description>
            </b2mml:PersonnelClassProperty>
          </b2mml:PersonnelClass>
          - <b2mml:QualificationTestSpecification>
            <b2mml:ID>2</b2mml:ID>
            <b2mml:Description>Experienced</b2mml:Description>
          </b2mml:QualificationTestSpecification>
        </Actor>
        + <Actor></Actor>
        + <Actor></Actor>
        + <Actor></Actor>
        + <Actor></Actor>
        + <Actor></Actor>
        + <Actor></Actor>
  
```

Figure 10: Information of CERTH/CPERI actors that are stored at repository

This component doesn't have a user interface because it will be running at the background supporting the communication a data exchange of the other components. The following figure shows a manual data retrieval from the repository, presenting information about the actors of CERTH/CPERI.

This information needs to be set out according to the agreed standards so that it can be recognizable and retractable. Thus, the information for such models (i.e. equipment, assets, actors, procedures, measurements, events, etc.) will be grouped following the hierarchy of the machinery components, subcomponents and topology, as well as the associations with the production activities.

Table 5: Information of the Status and the required input of the CIDEM

Status
The models have been defined and agreed, as well as specific details on the types to be adopted and used, in collaboration with other components too. It is very important that everyone keeps working using the specific B2MML types that have been agreed upon.
Required input
The sub-component of the Repository can be useful only if the respective models necessary have been made available by the end user to it. Moreover, the form that these models need to be available need to be compliant with CIDEM, based on B2MML types.

Estimation of delivery

The first version of the Repository is already available and supports all of the discussed protocols and standards. Minor modifications are needed towards expanding these models into a common framework in order to fully support the SatisFactory framework. A small set of the Models is needed by M17, so that this sub-component’s second version will be available by M19 to be tested at the Industry Lab from M20 and on.

3.2 OPERATIONAL PLATFORM WITH AUGMENTED INTELLIGENCE

The Operational Intelligence platform is responsible for providing real-time diagnostics and control actions to the operators at nominal conditions of shop floor operation as well as under conditions that require immediate attention and actions. The platform communicates directly with the middleware component and the DSS system in order to derive the optimum actions based on the current state of the machines and the worker’s behaviour. It is responsible for providing an overview of KPIs, personalized notes and tasks that are adjusted per worker. Additionally, the platform will integrate and present the Semantic Context and the Collaborative tools through an easy to use and intuitive interface.

Table 6: Information of the Status and the required input of the operational platform

Status
Due to the high dependency of the platform from other SatisFactory software components the implementation of the platform is at early stage. However the overall design and the core functionalities of the platform have been discussed and agreed upon.
Required input
Given the overall nature of the Operational Intelligence platform, input from most of the SatisFactory

components must be provided through the middleware and the CIDEM. Furthermore, the platform should be able to communicate with the Intelligence platform for real-time and unobtrusive performance during shop floor repair/restore procedures.

Estimation of delivery

The implementation of the Operational Platform will be accelerated right after the delivery of the first parts of the iDSS on M15. Following the delivery of the first version of the integrated iDSS on M18, a more thorough implementation will commence leading to a first version of the platform in M20. The final version is expected to finish after the full integrated SatisFactory system which will be delivered on M30, and prior to the shop floor integration which will be completed on M32.

- Supporting BSC-5.1, the platform will provide real-time information regarding the equipment that has malfunctioned, guidance for repairing/restoring the malfunction through the integration with the platform, and finally personalized notes and tasks that are adjusted per worker.
- For BSC-5.2 the Operational platform will aid by providing real-time current state for the equipment in hand along with AR instructions for the start-up process. Personalized notes and specific tasks per worker will also be provided, improving thus, both in aspects of performance and speed, the start-up process.
- The Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence will operate within BSC-5.3 as an optimization tool. By real-time communication with the middleware and the iDSS the platform will be able to extract and present optimal courses of actions for the improvement of the shop floor process flow based on the equipment's state as well as the personnel's behaviour. Operators will have the capability to observe these suggestions along with the possible outcome from each course of action.

3.3 SEMANTIC CONTEXT MANAGER - ONTOLOGY MANAGER

The Semantic Context Manager (SCM) has a layered structure (top, middle and low level). Each layer characterizes the specific type of aggregation (or classification) that is performed on the datasets (see D2.2). Shop floor XML data are extracted from the CIDEM, transformed into RDF/XML triplets and then stored within the SCM repository. These transformed datasets will contain instance records, with the structural relationships amongst the data and their attributes and concepts defined via ontologies. Datasets within a given SCM Web Service instance are exposed as Linked Data and may be accessed directly via API or via SPARQL queries. Therefore, at the top level of SCM, concepts and relations related to a specific BSC are defined and modelled as semantic models (ontologies). Such models help to make explicit the semantics of the given domain and provide the basis to reason or infer over it.

The following figure presents an instance of the Ontology Manager editor with the 3 Ontology Manager layers together with the first level of sub-concepts.

Figure 11: The Ontology Manager Editor

So far, according to the methodology that has been exploited to develop the semantic models for SatisFactory (described in D2.2), the BSC5 is investigated as a whole. Moreover, BSC-5.1, BSC-5.2 and BSC-5.3 share most of the concepts and knowledge sources. Thus, the actual BSC5 semantic model conceives of concepts that are described in the following table.

Table 7: Semantic Model of BSC-5

Concept	Description
<i>Worker</i>	Supervisors and Managers Operators and Technicians
<i>Pilot plant</i>	Small dedicated industrial system
<i>Procedure</i>	Planned activity to perform within the pilot plant
<i>Data</i>	Information data, can be either static or dynamic (often called “functions”)
<i>Component</i>	Simple component of the pilot plant
<i>Physical Asset</i>	Equipment, inventory or machines
<i>Action</i>	Action performed by the worker toward the completion of a specific procedure

The BSC-6.1 semantic model is focused on the concepts and relations that must be explicit in the context of workers safety. In particular, such ontology model conceives of concepts that are related with the areas in which workers are working in order to support the patch optimization for workers' movement. The main classes (concepts) of the model are described below.

Table 8: Semantic Model of BSC-6

Concept	Description
<i>Worker</i>	Operators and Technicians
<i>Pilot Plant</i>	Small dedicated industrial system
<i>Area</i>	Accessible or Forbidden Area
<i>Action</i>	Action performed by the user

Just like the other semantic models, these concepts will drive the semantic lifting of the XML data and put the basis to semantically search information that might support the end user in the specific application scenario.

Table 9: Information of the Status and the required input of the SCM

Status
<p>The BSC5 ontology model have been created locally and then deployed on an Ubuntu Virtual Machine provided by CERTH/CPERI. Such semantic model is made of concepts and relations that will drive the semantic lifting of the XML data and put the basis to semantically search information that might support the end user in the specific application scenario.</p> <p>The first tests of the Semantic context Manager, which are scheduled for M16 (by the end of April 2016), will help the further development and characterization of the component.</p> <p>Moreover, as a result of such tests, the possibility of a further “ramification” of the BSC5 model will be taken into consideration.</p> <p>The BSC6 ontology have been deployed on a virtual machine and already tested on a local machine to see how sample RDF instances can be SPARQL queried and what kind of assessment can be performed. Further refinement of the model will be put into practice during the first tests of the SCM, which are scheduled for M16.</p>
Required input
<p>Sample data will be provided by CERTH in order to test and refine the semantic models.</p> <p>Lists of concepts (information) related to each BSC can be very useful in other to check the completeness of the taxonomies proposed by the semantic models. Such lists can be created by EPFL in collaboration with the interested industrial partner.</p> <p>Few examples (i.e. two) of queries related to each Business Scenario should be provided by CERTH/CPERI in order to define what kind of analysis/request might be performed by the end user.</p>

Estimation of delivery

Sample data needed to test the every Business Scenario can be retrieved through the CIDEM at M15. The SCM is setup and fully deployed within the virtual machine of CERTH/CPERI shop floor at M16. During this period preliminary transformations are performed on datasets. Semantic searches and tests can be run on the virtual machine.

A set of queries provided by the industrial partner is implemented and tested on the VM at M16-M19. The final version of semantic model is provided together with the second iteration of D2.2 to begin the operational phase at M19.

The semantic model for each Business Scenario is accessible from the CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

3.4 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT PLATFORM – MY FACTORY – GAMIFICATION-BASED TOOLS

The “My Factory” component of the Suggestions for Improvement is a platform created for the workers mainly for the purpose of submitting suggestions to improve the process. Workers can also view suggestions submitted by others.

Table 10: Information of the Status and the required input of the gamification tools

Status
The prototyping and user evaluations for the “My Factory” component are complete. It is currently in data model design phase.
Required input
It is an independent component that doesn’t require any input from any other external system. However, it shares the database with the “My Factory Management” component for having a shared pool of suggestions. Also, it communicates with the gamification platform to create a game and to convey when a user performs a certain task and is supposed to be awarded with respective points for it.

Estimation of delivery

An initial version of the “My Factory” component of Suggestions for Improvement Platform will be deployable by the end of August (M20).

3.5 SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT PLATFORM – MY FACTORY MANAGEMENT – GAMIFICATION-BASED TOOLS

The “My Factory Management” component of the Suggestions for Improvement is a platform created for the management mainly for the purpose of taking decisions on the suggestions submitted by the workers in order to improve the process. The suggestions are assigned to different categories and for each category there is person responsible for taking decisions. The responsible person can also collaborate with others to take a decision, if need be.

Table 11: Information of the Status and the required input of the gamification tools

Status
The prototyping and user evaluations for the “My Factory Management” component are complete. It is currently in data model design phase.
Required input
It is an independent component that doesn’t require any input from any other external system. However, it shares the database with the “My Factory” component for having a shared pool of suggestions.

Estimation of delivery

An initial version of the “My Factory” component of Suggestions for Improvement Platform will be deployable by the mid of September (M21).

3.6 GAMIFICATION FRAMEWORK – GAMIFICATION-BASED TOOLS

The gamification framework is a central framework used to manage all the details of the gamification to be implemented at the factory. This means that the gamification framework provides certain APIs to the external systems e.g. Suggestions Platform, in order to enable them to create games, add tasks to these games and allocate points to these tasks. The gamification framework consists of a database that contains all the data related to all the games created by all the external systems utilizing the gamification framework. The cumulative scores are communicated to the workers via the digital screen and individual points via the “What’s My Score” component.

Table 12: Information of the Status and the required input of the gamification framework

Status
The design phase of the gamification framework is complete. Other than a few changes (if need be) it is ready to be implemented.
Required input
The gamification framework is to be used by other SatisFactory components in order to create games, add tasks and calculate points. This input shall be provided by the other SatisFactory components depending on their specific usage scenarios. Avatars, points, badges and rewards need to be configured inside the gamification framework by a stakeholder of the end user partner.

Estimation of delivery

An initial version of the Gamification Framework will be deployable by the end of August (M20).

3.7 GAMIFICATION FRAMEWORK – “WHAT’S MY SCORE” APP – GAMIFICATION-BASED TOOLS

“What’s My Score” is a mobile app mainly for the purpose of communicating individual scores to the workers. The app consists of the concept of avatar evolution, which means that in the beginning every worker is assigned an avatar and as his points increase, his avatar improves as well. The purpose of this app is to increase the worker’s awareness of his current performance with respect to each external system linked with the gamification platform.

Table 13: Information of the Status and the required input of the gamification framework

Status
Currently, the app is in prototyping phase.
Required input
The app requires the individual points of each worker and his current avatar from the central database of the gamification framework.

Estimation of delivery

An initial version of the Gamification Framework will be deployable by the end of August (M20).

3.8 MIDDLEWARE – DEVICE MANAGER

The Device Manager is a software component which provides integration of heterogeneous devices at middleware level (Linksmart). It is a set of components developed on the basis of specific technologies to be adapted, which have different implementations fulfilling the following functionalities:

- Implementation of technology-dependant APIs or protocols to handle specific IoT physical objects.
- Provisioning, over available networks and appropriate protocols (MQTT, REST, Web Services), actual devices data and measurements.
- Devices presence management and device resources availability propagation at middleware level (LinkSmart Resource Catalogue).

In this scenario, UWB devices, wireless temperature sensor and gesture recognition devices have been integrated.

Table 14: Information of the Status and the required input of the Device Manager

Status
The first basic – working – integration of UWB localization devices, wireless temperature sensor and gesture recognition devices have been performed, leveraging the MQTT protocol to share data and the REST-based component to subscribe devices and related services on the Resource/Service Catalogue.
Required input
Apart from technology specific knowledge necessary to interact with involved devices, it was required the functional specification of Resource Catalogue and Service Catalogue.

Estimation of delivery

First version of the Device manager will be deployed at the CERTH/CPERI shop-floor at M19.

3.9 MIDDLEWARE - CORE SERVICES

LinkSmart middleware services provide a main to register and discover devices and services in a LinkSmart eco-system. Integration of smart sensors, depth sensors and localization manager with LinkSmart is done by implementing LinkSmart APIs by Device Managers. Documentation, functional specification and also a Java SDK of the APIs assist the use case components for smooth device integration. Device Managers are registered into resource catalogue with a Registration document.

Table 15: Information of the Status and the required input of the middleware core services

Status
Recently LinkSmart has gone through major architectural and design changes. An initial version of the LinkSmart middleware with support of standard and lightweight protocols has been released and ready to be used by Satisfactory components.
Required input
It has no dependency on other use-case components.

Estimation of delivery

LinkSmart middleware has already been deployed at the pilot site and its response/operation will be tested/used by the other components.

3.10 MIDDLEWARE - EVENT MANAGER

It supports publish-subscribe based messaging pattern through lightweight MQTT protocol. It is a central message broker that supports communication between Device Managers and high level services/components taking part in this business scenario. Upon registration into resource catalogue, device managers configure the topics on which data is being published. Therefore, services are required to learn the designated topics from resource catalogue.

Table 16: Information of the Status and the required input of the Event Manager

Status
Event Manager supporting MQTT protocol version 3.1 is available.
Required input
LinkSmart core services need to be up and running. It is register as a broker service in a Service Catalogue.

Estimation of delivery

Event Manager has also been deployed at the pilot site and its response/operation will be tested/used by the other components.

3.11 MIDDLEWARE - EVENT AGGREGATOR

Many use-case components like automation system, sensors network and localization manager would like to store events and notifications in a CIDEM repository. Components like iDSS and Semantic Context Manager process this store data to extract and establish useful information. Event Aggregator resides on the LinkSmart side and subscribes to the Event Broker to get notified of the events being published by these components and later store these events in a CIDEM repository. All events/notifications are supposed to be CIDEM compliant.

Table 17: Information of the Status and the required input of the Event Aggregator

Status:
It is currently under development.
Required Input:
LinkSmart core services need to be up and running. CIDEM repository service is also available.

Estimation of delivery

It is expected that the initial version will be deployed at the pilot site in M17 and its response/operation will be tested/used by the other components.

4 BSC-5.1 - REPAIR OR RESTORE AN ELECTROMECHANICAL MALFUNCTION

The goal of chapter 4 is to describe the planning for implementation and the initial setup and usage of the available components/tools at the scenario BSC-5.1.

Application Scenario BSC-5.1 is about corrective actions that need immediate attention. There exist various possible malfunctions during the normal operation of a pilot plant. Some of them can be treated after the current operation is completed while others need immediate attention in order for the pilot plant to continue the schedule actions. An electromechanical malfunction needs immediate care to avoid safety issues as well. This Application Scenario describes all the necessary actions in order to repair this kind of malfunctions and continue the normal operation of a pilot plant.

Goals:

- Perform work to repair or replace a faulty or degraded equipment

Objectives

- Reduce the time to respond to a malfunction
- Automatically provide appropriate information for the evaluation of the fault and the necessary actions to be applied by the involved actors

Figure 12: General information flow and sequence of activities of BSC-5.1

There are various possible malfunctions during the normal operation of a pilot plant. One of them could be an electromechanical malfunction which needs immediate care in order not to interrupt the

normal operation of the pilot plant and to avoid safety issues as well. Possible malfunctions are burned out fuses, burned out resistors and malfunctioning solid state relays. AR tools, the iDSS and the Content Management tools could help the technician to isolate the malfunction and repair or replace the faulty equipment with minimum or no downtime of the operation of the Pilot Plant and not losing any data of the ongoing experiment continuing as if the problem not occurred at all.

At each heating zone of the reactor there is a signal for the temperature and the controller. The process operator inserts the desired temperature set-point and a conventional PI controller is used to read the desired level of operation and to maintain the temperature at the specific set-point. When a malfunction occurs at a heating zone of the reactor then the automation technician examines 2 main cases in order to determine the cause of the problem. The process operator monitors the process through the HMI of the automation system. In case an abnormal situation occurs, he provides the initial notification to the technical team.

- **Case 1:** The process operator observes that the temperature has a large undershoot against the desired set-point of operation while the controller output is 100%.
- **Case 2:** The process operator observes that the temperature has a large overshoot against the desired set-point of operation while the controller output is 0%.

Preconditions:

- Existing of faulty or degraded equipment
- The SCADA system gives an alarm of abnormal behavior of a thermocouple
- All the thermocouples of the pilot plant is correctly mounted

Materials involved:

- Fuse
- Solid State Relay
- Terminals
- Resistor
- Multimeter
- Wires

Table 18: Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for the BSC-5.1

1) The operator or the SCADA system identifies a malfunction
2) The operator declares the new job at the iDSS
3) The technician receives the ticket for the new job and moves to the point that the system has identified
4) The technician opens the door of the electrical enclosure
5) The AR tool (e.g. tablet) displays the appropriate electrical drawings to the technician
6) The AR tool locates the involved fuse, screw terminals and solid state relay and magnifies on them at the schematics
7) If there is a hihi alarm the technician checks the solid state relay. If not go to step 14
8) After that the technician removes the appropriate fuse

9) The operator must set manual 0 at the output of the controller at the SCADA system
10) The technician removes the wires of the relay and replaces it
11) The technician connects back the fuse
12) The operator starts the auto function of the controller
13) The operator gives feedback whether the problem has been solved or not
14) If there is a lolo alarm the technician removes the appropriate fuse and checks it with the multimeter
15) The operator must set manual 0 at the output of the controller at the SCADA system
16) If the fuse is burned out, the technician replaces it
17) The AR tool indicates where the resistor is located
18) The technician removes the wires of the resistor from the terminals
19) The technician measures the resistor with the multimeter
20) If the resistor is burned out the technician replaces it
21) If not he connects back the fuse and the resistor wires
22) The technician takes a snapshot of the area where the equipment is placed and the AR tool displays a list with all the parts that exist at that point (from the identified assets as described at P&ID)
23) The technician choses the equipment that was involved along with the actions taken and the results
24) The AR tool sends feedback to the iDSS for the specific job (which was declared at step 2.

The next figure is showing the electrical cabinet of the pilot plant of BSC-5.1. The malfunction that is described at the scenario will happen at a part that is mounted inside this cabinet

Figure 13 Electrical cabinet at of a pilot plant at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI

4.1 SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS USED

For the implementation of the BSC-5.1 a set of components of the Satisfactory platform will be used in order to realize the procedures and activities of the scenarios. Figure 14 shows the subset of the components that are invoked to be used by the scenario, at least in its current form according to the feedback and collaboration achieved during T5.3.

Figure 14: Visualization of the utilized components of the Satisfactory Architecture at BSC-5.1

Table 19 presents the components that are common at BSC-5.1. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 19: Identified Components to be utilized at BSC-5.1

Responsible partner	
CERTH	<p>Component: Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC)</p> <p>Restrictions: The PDEC must have a continuous operation because pilot plants at CERTH/CPERI shop floor are on 24 hours.</p> <p>Prerequisites: OPC connection between the SCADA systems and the PDEC</p>
ISMB	<p>Component: Middleware – Device Manager</p> <p>Restrictions: Device manager is involved in the case of usage of some environmental data acquisition device. It should be technically possible to integrate involved devices through the device manager</p> <p>Prerequisites: Involved devices API and usage manual availability</p>

ISMB	<p>Component: Context-Aware Manager - Multimedia Manager</p> <p>Restrictions: Only video distribution is provided by this component with deferred video distributed in case of incident</p>
ABE	<p>Component: Integrated DSS</p> <p>Restrictions: The malfunction must be identified outside of Integrated DSS and the notification must be fed to the DSS core</p> <p>Prerequisites: Availability of analytical maintenance procedures from the shop floors</p>
REGOLA	<p>Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools</p> <p>Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves</p>
REGOLA	<p>Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job</p> <p>Restrictions: The identification of the malfunction + notification of it + selection of maintenance procedure must be made by a higher level system. The presentation tools instead will present information about process conditions from this higher system and will interactively visualize the selected maintenance procedure to support actors to solve the fault</p> <p>Prerequisites: Formalized maintenance operating procedures to solve the fault. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves</p>
REGOLA	<p>Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework</p> <p>Restrictions: The Simulated Framework will be used to test the maintenance procedure only</p> <p>Prerequisites: Formalized maintenance operating procedures to solve the fault. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves</p>
GlassUP	<p>Component: Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI</p> <p>Restrictions: Glasses both to show repair instructions to the user, and to send images / video of the issues to the manager.</p>

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

4.1.1 Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC

This software component will support the transmission and transformation of the shop floor data to ISA-95 complaint format. It combines diverse data from shop-floor automation systems and the IoT sensors to support decision making, in events related to production activities, in smart factory incidents, etc. It can be promoted in two stages.

First, as a component of the automation system at in-house process systems. Secondly, it can be provided as a service to companies that already have process systems. The PDEC will collect all the useful information of the Pilot Plants that are involved in SatisFactory and distribute them to other

components (like Linksmart, CIDEM, etc.) through web services according to ISA-95. The PDEC will translate OPC data to B2MML format and make them available through RESTful services.

Figure 15: Overview window of the user interface of the PDEC

PDEC has various information about the connection and the communication of the automation system of the shop floor with the SatisFactory components. The following figure shows the Overview window of the interface of the component. The status of all the pilot plants at the shop floor, the communication methods that are used and the sampling setting can be seen at this window. Exploring to the other tabs, the user is able to see details about the data that are being sent from the automation system to the other components.

Table 20: Information of the Status and the required input of the PDEC

Status
The development and testing of the PDEC is completed and the software has been installed at CERTH/CPERI shop floor. There have been many tests and reconfigurations in order to be more effective and compliant with the other components of SatisFactory. At M16 the component started the nominal and continuous operation at the shop floor, sending data to the other components that have been installed at CERTH/CPERI shop floor.
Required input
The inputs of PDEC are the data of the pilot plants at CERTH/CPERI shop floor. It also receives feedback from the other components, according to the needs of each business scenario.

Estimation of delivery

The component has been delivered and installed at CETH/CPERI shop floor at M16. The implementation of the bidirectional communication will be invoked at a later stage (M20-M24) as the components that will provide the notification information where not available at this stage.

4.1.2 Context-Aware Manager - Multimedia Manager

The Multi-Media manager is a component responsible for distributing media from the shop floor to SatisFactory components. It is also responsible for handling and handling and signaling WebRTC protocol to connect shop-floor location.

Table 21: Information of the Status and the required input of the Multi-Media manager

Status
<p>Current status is the Multi-Media Manager acquires the video from the smart assembly station using the same acquisition hardware of the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager and distributes it using MotionJPEG encoding. Also a deferred video feature is available in case of incident in order to be able to visualize the incident that has occurred from a remote location.</p> <p>WebRTC communication has been tested, but has not been integrated in the current version, yet. More stability and performance tests are required.</p>
Required input
<p>The Multi-Media Manager module requires a configuration file that will be stored in the CIDEM and loaded through LinkSmart during the startup process.</p>

Estimation of delivery

The first set of features is expected to be deployed at CETH/CPERI at M17. Afterwards the WebRTC communication and signaling will be integrated and ready at M20.

4.1.3 Integrated DSS

The Integrated DSS (iDSS) within the SatisFactory architecture (as described in D2.1 in M8) is a complex tool comprised by 5 sub-components, namely: DSS-Core, Maintenance Toolkit, Shop floor Feedback Engine, Incident Management Tools, Visual and Real-time Analytics Module. It also interacts with other components in order to carry out a specific task. The next figure shows the web-based UI of the iDSS component.

Figure 16: The web interface of the iDSS

In this scenario it is envisaged that the following sub-components will be used: DSS-Core, Maintenance Procedures, Shop floor Feedback Engine, Incident Management Tools, Maintenance Toolkit, Real-time Analytics and maybe Visual Analytics Module. The main component is the DSS Core, which is responsible for orchestrating all the rest of the subcomponents, for ensuring that the output of each subcomponent is using the right channel and the appropriate format in order to be directed to external components and that external components can subscribe and be actually notified by the various events raised from DSS subcomponents. The mobile UI of the component is being shown at the following figure. The first instance shows the application at a login phase and the second shows when a worker has completed successfully a task that he was assigned.

Figure 17: Two instances of the mobile UI of the iDSS component

The iDSS within BSC-5.1 will receive a notification of an alarm by the automation system. An early detection possibility is being investigated using Real-time Analytics. The information will be fed to the Incident Management Tools and it will trigger the DSS Core to interact with Maintenance Procedures and the Maintenance Toolkit. Thus, the system will be able to provide suggestions on the responsive actions required, along with the information necessary, which reside in the Repository. The information will be combined in the Shop floor Feedback Engine and it will be redirected to the corresponding visualization sub-component. Both the UI of the iDSS (web-based and mobile) are in a test period and the information that will be received from the usage at CERTH/CPERI premises will help for the improvement of the component.

Table 22: Information of the Status and the required input of the iDSS

Status
The development of the sub-components of the iDSS has begun, with the main focus being up to this point in the DSS-Core, Maintenance Procedures, Incident Management Tools and Maintenance Toolkit.
Required input
For iDSS to operate in BSC-5.1 the malfunction must be identified outside of Integrated DSS and the notification must be fed to the DSS core from the automation system and/or the smart sensor network in near real-time. Moreover, the analytical maintenance procedures need to be made available from the shop floor involved and the related material and information to be made available at the Repository. Additionally, inferred ontologies from the Ontology Manager need to be available for inquiring.

Estimation of delivery

The first version of the iDSS with the sub-components necessary for the implementation of this specific Business Scenario is anticipated to be ready by M18. Several parts of the tool will be made gradually available from M15 and on, in order to test the information flow applicability. An initial demo prototype will be made available for the Hannover Messe exhibition.

4.1.4 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools

The AR SOP Creation Tool is the application that will be used in the factory context to define and edit the procedure in order to show it by means of the AR Visualization Tool.

The AR Creation Tool is based on two modules:

- The resource module
- The operating procedure module.

The **resource module** allows for the creation of a resource repository that can be used by any procedure. It allows the resource definition, supporting as resources: images, video, 3d models, documents and so on.

The **Operating procedure module** allows for the definition of a procedure in terms of its own steps, namely:

- Operations
- Phases
- Actions
- The relationships connecting them.

A complete procedure definition will produce as output a graph enabling the procedure execution according to a well-defined navigation model.

To support the procedure definition, the AR Creation Tool makes available an inventory allowing the definition of all the elements required to execute the procedure.

Each element in the procedure (operation, phase, action, relationship) may be described in terms of its own base elements. The maximum possible level of detail is in the Action, featuring a Descriptive Layer.

The Descriptive Layer make possible to describe each action with different contents:

- simple text
- images
- videos
- 3d models.

Please, note, it is not mandatory to insert all the possible Descriptive Layers for each single action; only those related to a specific content to be used to describe the Action are required.

It is possible to define the list of the objects required to execute the action getting them from the inventory already filled by means of elements such: Components, Equipment and Tools.

The sequence of the Actions to be executed is produced by the Relationships due to the fact that, in facts, the Relationships define an ordering along the Action sequences. They are:

- Consecutive
- Undefined
- Conditional
- Repeated
- Other.

The procedure defined so far could be exported as a bundle to be saved in the repository of the Operative Procedures or Maintenance Procedures.

Table 23: Information of the Status and the required input of the AR SOP Creation Tool

Status
The AR SOP Creation Tool development is almost nearly completed
Required input
The data required as input for the AR SOP Creation Tool is the operating procedure description and all types of content able to provide a detailed and complete description of it. This information must be provided by CERTH .

Estimation of delivery

The delivery date for the BSC-5-1 is on M19, after completion of third-party components (middleware, satisfactory repository) by M18.

About BSC.5-1.

In the BSC-5.1 the AR OP Creation Tool will be used to define the resources and the inventory required by the procedure (images, videos, etc.) according to the procedure definition along the steps 3-24 in terms of Operations, Phases, Actions and Relationships. Other steps could be better arranged using the AR Presentation Tool.

4.1.5 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job

The AR Presentation Tool is the software able to navigate the bundle that is the output of the Creation Tool. It has the capability of navigate the procedure step by step, following sequences, loops and conditions included in the procedure and, in doing this, it delivers the content which has been previously managed and included as resource by the Creation Tool.

The content delivered could depend on the capabilities of the platform, so, for example, the operator will be exposed to video, sound, images, 3D models etc. depending on the fact that h/w platform can render that kind of content. Furthermore, the operator has the opportunity to choose the best content that fit its own needs within the contents that can be deployed and delivered in the platform he/she is actually using.

In this model, the AR content is one of several content types that can be made available in the AR Presentation Tool; it can be triggered in the following different ways:

- marker based; i.e., by means of the recognition of an high contrast, traditional markers that provide the anchor to which the AR content is bound
- Feature based; i.e., by means of the recognition of a general image featuring enough complexity to be uniquely identified, so providing the anchor to which the AR content is bound.

The Presentation Tool could be deployed on several platforms, being able, as told, to adapt the content presented to the operator to its own capabilities.

Table 24: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
The development of the AR SOP Presentation Tool is almost completed
Required input
A name that uniquely identifies the procedure to be performed

Estimation of delivery

The delivery date for the BSC-5-1 is on M20, if third-party components (middleware, satisfactory repository) are completed not later than M18.

4.1.6 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework

The Presentation Tool could be used in a simulated framework. The immersion in the target environment is not required to:

- navigate the procedure step by step
- Be exposed to the content included in that step.

This simulation framework allows for review of the procedure and its contents, for learning, for testing, without the need for reality hooks able to trigger the AR content.

Table 25: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
The development of the AR SOP Presentation Tool is almost nearly completion
Required input
A name that uniquely identifies the procedure to be performed

Estimation of delivery

The delivery date for the BSC-5-1 is on M20 if third-party components (middleware, satisfactory repository) are completed not later than M18.

4.1.7 Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI

Glassup devices are AR Glasses designed to be worn by shop floor workers, thus providing them with sensors, camera and a display to show relevant information about working environment and surroundings. In this scenario, the AR Glasses will show shop floor workers all required instructions in order to repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction. The worker will be able to navigate through the different steps of the repair procedure and to send the video taken from the on-board camera to senior workers asking for help.

Table 26: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
A prototype of the Glasses is under construction, in the meanwhile the API list is almost completed and soon the implementation of the SDK will begin.
Required input
The required input for AR glasses is the maintenance procedure to be shown to the worker subdivided in the various steps and other useful information related to the topic. All information should come from the Repository and forwarded to the Glasses by specific mobile applications developed by Regola

Estimation of delivery

At the beginning of M18 Glassup will deliver a document with API specification to the partners, whereas the SDK will be ready at M20, together with the first hardware prototype.

4.2 SATISFACTORY ACTORS INVOLVED

The actors at SatisFactory are being separated at groups, different in each shop floor. Every group has one or more employees who perform the same kind of tasks inside the shop floors. An actor can be experienced, trainee or novice. Detailed analysis of the actors has been help for the purposes of the deliverable D1.2. The following table shows the groups of actors that are involved at BSC-5.1.

Table 27: List with the SatisFactory actors' groups that are involved at BSC-5.1

BSC 5.1	Groups of actors
	Maintenance manager
	Electrical technician
	Process technician
	Automation technician

	Process operator
	Process supervisor

4.3 STATUS OF THE BUSINESS SCENARIO 5.1

Business Scenario 5.1 will come as a great assistance to the workers of CETH/CPERI regarding some of their procedures at the shop floor. There have been many tests and a detailed analysis during the design phase of each component in order to determine their usability and to increase the positive effect that they will have to the workers. The BSC-5.1 will increase the safety at the shop floor, will enhance the involved workers at the needed actions and contribute at their general satisfaction. The following table presents the status of all involved components at BSC-5.1.

Table 28 : Gantt Diagram with the implementation of the components involved at BSC-5.1

	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20
BSC-5.1 – Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction								
Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Context-Aware Manager - Multimedia Manager		Design		Set-up	Deployment		Operation	
Integrated DSS	Design	Set-up		Deployment		Operation		
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools		Design		Set-up	Deployment		Operation	
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job		Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework		Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation
Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses		Design			Set-up	Deployment		Operation
GENERAL COMPONENTS								
Repository-Asset machinery, production models	Design	Set-up			Deployment			Operation
Operational platform with augmented intelligence	Design	Set-up			Deployment		Operation	
Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager	Design	Set-up			Deployment		Operation	
Suggestion for improvement platform - My Factory - Gamification - based tools		Design				Set-up	Deployment	Operation
Suggestions for Improvement – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools		Design				Set-up	Deployment	
Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools		Design			Set-up	Deployment		Operation
Gamification Framework – “What’s My Score” App – Gamification-based tools		Design			Set-up	Deployment		Operation
Middleware – Device Manager	Design		Set-up			Deployment		Operation
Middleware - Core Services	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Middleware - Event Manager	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Event Aggregator	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				

Where the operation phase is missing from a component, this means that it is scheduled after month 20 (M20). The operation of the installed components/tools that start within the timeframe of the Table 28 will continue towards the 2nd iteration of T5.3 activities until M24.

5 BSC-5.2 – STARTUP PROCEDURES FOR PILOT PLANTS

The goal of chapter 5 is to describe the planning for implementation and the initial setup and initial usage of the available components/tools at the scenario BSC-5.2. Business Scenario BSC-5.2 is about the critical start-up step of operating hydroprocessing pilot plants and involves the loading of the feed tank, as the first step of the overall experimental plan, which needs to be carefully performed to allow the optimal feedstock introduction in the downstream catalytic system. The proper feed tank loading is the result of starting the recycling pump and systematically heating the feed lines according to the specific feedstock quality characteristics and experimental run objectives set the process supervisor and implementing the loading strategy by the process technician. It is also important that feed tank loading follows the proper maintenance of the hydroprocessing plant, to allow technical problems during the future experimental run. This Application Scenario has as a goal to make sure that the proper steps will be followed even from workers with small experience.

Goals:

- Nominal startup of a pilot plant based on standard operating procedures
- Create a Standard Operating Procedure for starting/operating/shutdown a pilot plant

Objective:

- Reduce startup time
- Avoid errors during the startup procedures

The challenge is to create a standard procedure for starting up a pilot plant in order first to reduce startup time and second to avoid errors during the startup procedures increasing the safety and reducing stress. The final goal is to Startup the pilot plant with no errors or conflicts and with the least usage of recourses (time consumed, actors involved, materials and tools needed).

Preconditions:

- All lines, feed containers, reactor and separator system should be clean
- Reactor should be loaded with catalyst
- Successfully passed pressure test

Materials involved:

- Recycling pump P51A
- Feed container
- 3-way valve 5HV-52A
- Feed intake line
- Scale
- Pressure control valve PCV-51A
- Pressure indicator PI-53A
- Weight transmitter WT-51A

- Sample bottle
- Hood
- Glass door

Table 29: Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for the BSC-5.2

1) Enable the pump interface by setting it ON from unit PC
2) Place container close to the recycling pump
3) Bring the feed intake line next to the recycling pump
4) Hood removal
5) Feed container shaking
6) Open feed container lid
7) Place the long side of the feed intake line on the feed container
8) Connect the other side of the feed intake line to the 3-way valve
9) Place the hood on top of the feed container
10) Open the glass door in front of the feed container
11) Press the zero button on the scale
12) Open the 3-way valve by turning it to be aligned with the feed intake line
13) Start the pump by pressing the ON/OFF button (if ON a green light will be displayed)
14) Open and close the 2HV valve until liquid flows
15) Loosen the PCV-51A
16) Observe on the WT-51 the gradual weight increase
17) Press the TIC-51A button to start the temperature increase in the feed container and the associated lines
18) Wait until the desired feed quantity is loaded
19) Switch off the 3-way valve opposing the direction of the feed intake line
20) Remove the feed intake line
21) Place feed container lid and close it
22) Remove feed container
23) Clean feed intake line
24) Store feed intake line
25) Close the glass door of the feed container
26) Bring the waste container
27) Open the lid of the waste container
28) Empty the glass bottle of the valve 2HV-54A outlet to the waste container
29) Close the lid of the waste container
30) Close the lid of the glass bottle we just emptied
31) Clean the 3-way valve inlet with paper
32) Store the waste container

Figure 18 VB01 hydro processing Pilot Plant at CERN/CPERI shop floor

A mock-up of the operation using AR tools is created and tested at the shop-floor environment (Figure 19 AR Training Proof-of-Concept app using Fiducially Markers).

Figure 19 AR Training Proof-of-Concept app using Fiducially Markers

5.1 SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS USED

For the implementation of the BSC-5.2 a set of components of the SatisFactory platform will be used in order to realize the procedures and activities of the scenarios. Figure 20 shows the subset of the components that are invoked to be used by the scenario, at least in its current form according to the feedback and collaboration achieved during task T5.3.

Figure 20: Visualization of the utilized components of the SatisFactory Architecture at BSC-5.2

Table 30 presents the components that are common at BSC-5.2. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 30: Identified Components to be utilized at BSC-5.2

Responsible partner	
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job Restrictions: The presentation tools will be visualize all and only the supported contents (images, text, icons) Prerequisites: Clear and effective messages (images, text, icons) have to be generated at runtime by external specialized components and sent to AR Tools that will present these contents in pre-designed HMIs
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves
CERTH	Component: Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC) Restrictions: The PDEC must have a continuous operation because pilot plants at CERTH/CPERI shop floor are

	on 24 hours. Prerequisites: OPC connection between the SCADA systems and the PDEC
GlassUP	Component: Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI
ISMB	Restrictions: Glasses used to display text and image instructions to user. Component: Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager Prerequisites: List of assembly procedure instructions (JPEG, PNG or PDF), list of maintenance or supervision mode instructions (JPEG, PNG or PDF), checklist for final recap (e.g. BOM) in XML format Restrictions: Safety equipment recognized if necessary and machine learning regained in advance

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

5.1.1 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools

The AR SOP Creation Tool has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.4 . At the BSC-5.2, the AR SOP Creation Tool is used to provide assistance to the worker through the detailed standard operating procedures that will be created. This is a very helpful function which can help both experienced and novice employees.

5.1.2 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job

The AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.5 . At the BSC-5.2, this tool will be using the procedures that will be created from the AR SOP Creation Tools and present them to the workers who are using it. The combination of the above two components (and the one that follows) gives a complete solution ready to be used at the shop floor.

5.1.3 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework

The AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.6. It is used in combination with the AR SOP Creation Tools and the AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job.

5.1.4 Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC

The Plant Data Exchange Component has been described with details at section 4.1.1 . The BSC-5.2 uses PDEC to check some variables of the involved pilot plant and it also receives feedback regarding the actions of the operators.

5.1.5 Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI

The Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices component is also being used at BSC-5.1 and it has been analyzed at paragraph 4.1.7 . The worker will wear the smart glasses and he/she will be able to receive useful information about the actions that have to be done.

5.1.6 Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager

The Gesture & Content Recognition Manager is a headless module that is deployed to the smart assembly stations and is in charge of:

- capture user gestures for browsing through assembly instructions (Figure 21)
- require maintenance assistance triggering specific events
- implement a fall detection system (Figure 22)
- signaling presence of workers in the nearby area
- signaling assembly progress updates
- detect safety equipment wear by workers on the smart assembly stations (Figure 24)

The following figure shows two gestures of a worker that can be recognized from the system. This way the worker would be able to give command to the platform remotely while he is working on something in the shop floor. The upper left image shows a “LeftHandSwipeRight” gesture that is recognized from the system and the lower left image presents the message that is displayed at the interface of the component when this gesture is recognized. The upper right image shows a “BothHandsRaised” gesture that is recognized from the system and the lower right image presents the message that is displayed at the interface of the component when the gesture is recognized.

Figure 21: Recognition of worker's gesture

Figure 22 shows a case of a fall of a worker that can be recognised from the component. Immediately after a detection of an incident, a message to the platform is being sent and all involved components will be notified.

Figure 22: Fall detection at CErTH/CPERI shop floor

Furthermore, an application has been developed in order to test the functionality and the behaviour of falling detection function. Figure 23 shows the messages that are displayed at the test application when the component detects a fall of a worker. These messages are also being sent to the

SatisFactory platform in order to be used from all related components. This function focuses only to the station where the assembly and gesture related functionalities are provided to the workers. It increases the safety of the workers at the shop floor area and makes them feel more secure and confident.

Figure 23: Falling detection messages

The detection of safety equipment worn by workers is another function of the component as mentioned above. The safety equipment which can be detected is helmet, glasses and gloves. The next figure shows a fully equipped worker.

Figure 24: Fully equipped worker at CERTH/CPERI shop floor

The hardware that has been installed for this component is shown at the next two figures.

Figure 25: Kinect camera installed for the gesture component

Figure 26: NUC pc installed for the gesture component

Figure 25 shows the Kinect camera which captures the movements of the workers and Figure 26 shows the pc with the software of the component.

Table 31: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
The first version will deploy all the listed features, aside for the last one that still needs to be refined to work on the target hardware platform.
Required input
<p>The module requires the following input:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gestures from the worker on the smart assembly station • assembly instructions and checklist for being displayed on the digital andon system • bidimensional two axis positioning for providing localization information coherent with origin and coordinate system used by the localization manager

Estimation of delivery

The first version is expected to be deployed with the preliminary version of the aforementioned features available to CERTH/CPERI shop-floor at M18. It will start to operate in order to be tested and if needed to be optimized.

5.2 SATISFACTORY ACTORS INVOLVED

The actors at SatisFactory are being separated at groups, different in each shop floor. Every group has one or more employees who perform the same kind of tasks inside the shop floors. An actor can be experienced, trainee or novice. Detailed analysis of the actors has been help for the purposes of the deliverable D1.2. The following table shows the groups of actors that are involved at BSC-5.2.

Table 32: List with the SatisFactory actors' groups that are involved at BSC-5.2

BSC 5.2	Groups of actors
	Process operator
	Process supervisor
	Process technician
	Maintenance supervisor

5.3 STATUS OF THE BUSINESS SCENARIO 5.2

Business Scenario 5.2 is going to assist process operators and technicians in a standard procedure which includes the startup of a pilot plant. The operators will be enhanced by the actions of the scenario and they will be more confident about the procedures that they perform. There have been many tests and a detailed analysis during the design phase of each component in order to determine their usability and to increase the positive effect that they will have to the workers. The following table presents the status of all involved components at BSC-5.2.

Table 33: Gantt Diagram with the implementation of the components involved at BSC-5.2

	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20
BSC-5.2 – Startup procedures for pilot plants								
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job	Design	Set-up	Set-up	Deployment	Deployment	Operation		
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework	Design	Set-up	Set-up	Deployment	Operation			
Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Multi modal & Augmented HMLs and AR devices – Glasses UI	Design	Set-up	Set-up	Deployment	Operation			
Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
GENERAL COMPONENTS								
Repository-Asset machinery, production models	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Operational platform with augmented intelligence	Design	Set-up	Set-up	Deployment	Operation			
Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Suggestion for improvement platform - My Factory - Gamification - based tools	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Set-up	Deployment	Operation		
Suggestions for Improvement – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Set-up	Deployment			
Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools	Design	Set-up	Set-up	Deployment	Operation			
Gamification Framework – “What’s My Score” App – Gamification-based tools	Design	Set-up	Set-up	Deployment	Operation			
Middleware – Device Manager	Design	Set-up	Set-up	Deployment	Operation			
Middleware - Core Services	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Middleware - Event Manager	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Event Aggregator	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				

Where the operation phase is missing from a component, this means that it is scheduled after month 20 (M20). The operation of the installed components/tools that start within the timeframe of the Table 33 will continue towards the 2nd iteration of T5.3 activities until M24.

6 BSC-5.3 – RECONFIGURATION OF PROCESS FLOW AND ACTIONS FOR FLEXIBLE REDESIGN OF PRODUCTION PROCEDURES

The goal of chapter 6 is to describe the planning for implementation and the initial setup and initial usage of the available components/tools at the scenario BSC-5.3. This scenario of CERTH refers to the need to alter the operation of a pilot plant. A number of required actions need to be executed in order for the process configuration to be suitable for the new operation.

Goals:

- Improvement of process work flow for the reconfiguration of a multipurpose unit

Objectives:

- Provide alternatives based on predefined flows or past configurations
- Reduce the time needed for the pilot plant startup
- Avoid delays and failures during the reconfiguration between different workflow scenarios of a pilot plant

In this application scenario, since different gases are going to be used in the new operating conditions, the calibrated mass flow controllers along with the appropriate gas bottles need to be installed. Moreover, the automation system variables and alarm bounds have to be updated, while the method on the chromatograph also needs to be changed. Finally, the last action of the procedure before the pilot plant is ready to be used in the new operating conditions is to perform pressure tests using helium in order to detect possible leaks.

Alternatives based on:

- Input flows
- Input type of gases
- Combination of mixtures
- Input liquid products
- Operating ranges for temperature & pressure
- Reactor architecture

Basic Categories of performed actions:

- Install calibrated mass flow controllers (MFC)
- Install Appropriate gas bottles (GB)
- Update the automation system variables and alarm bound
- Change the method on the chromatograph
- Perform a pressure test

Preconditions:

- The operation of the pilot plant has finished and there is a need to start under different conditions. The SCADA system gives an alarm of abnormal behavior of a thermocouple
- Previous experiment: Methane steam reforming (0-5000cc/min CH₄, 5 barg, 500 °C, S/C = 3)
- Next experiment: Ethane steam reforming (0-3000 cc/min C₂H₆, 10 barg, 300 °C, S/C= 2)

Post conditions:

- **Success Guarantees:** Readaptation of production based on upcoming experiment needs
- **Failure end conditions:** Increment of the workflow complexity of the experiments

Materials involved:

- Mass Flow Controller (MFC) FV
- Mass Flow Controller (MFC) FV-21C
- Gas Bottles (GB)
- Gas Chromatograph
- Helium Leak Detector (HLD)

Table 34: Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for the BSC-5.3

1)	Identify the MFC that need to be replaced (Methane -> Ethane, FT/FV-21C)
2)	The volumetric flow rate range required at the previous experiment is 0-5000 cc/min, while the next experiment is 0-3000 cc/min, thus another MFC, calibrated for Ethane, should be installed.
3)	Calibrate the new MFC according to the gas (ethane) and the flowrate (0-3000 cc/min) to be used (if needed)
4)	Uninstall the previous MFC and install the new MFC
5)	Identify the GB that need to be replaced (Methane -> Ethane)
6)	Make sure that the valve of the GB is closed
7)	Remove the previously used GB (methane)
8)	Install the new GB (ethane)
9)	Update the ranges of the installed MFC in the HMI Database. The new MFC's volumetric flow rate range is 0-3000 cc/min.
10)	Update the upper and lower boundaries of alarms in the HMI Database. Volumetric flow rate (0-3000 cc /min), pressure (0-10 bar) and temperature (0-300 °C) boundaries need to be updated.
11)	Change the method that is used in the chromatograph so that the new outlet stream's composition can be identified. The previous method is "SYNGAS22.M" while the new one to be used is "SYNEX21.M"
12)	After everything (MFC & GB) have been installed in the pilot plant a pressure test needs to be performed in order to check for possible leaks before operating the unit.
13)	In order to perform a pressure loss test Valves HV-81 (or HV-80) and 6HV-81 needs to be (manually) closed.
14)	Subsequently nitrogen is introduced into the system by setting the appropriate MFC's (FC-21C) volumetric flow rate at 200 cc/min.
15)	When the pressure at PI-81 reaches 10 bar (depending on the reaction's conditions), the flow rate is set to 0 cc/min and Valve XV-21C is closed.
16)	The pressure loss test is performed overnight, pressurizing by mean of Valve XV-21C and HV-81. If loss of pressure exceeds 5% overnight, or the leaking flow exceeds 2cc/min, then check for leaks with Helium Leak Detector (HLD)

Figure 27 SynGas Pilot Plant at CETH/CPERI shop floor

6.1 SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS USED

For the implementation of the BSC-5.3 a set of components of the SatisFactory platform will be used in order to realize the procedures and activities of the scenarios. Figure 28 shows the subset of the components that are invoked to be used by the scenario, at least in its current form according to the feedback and collaboration achieved during T5.3. Each one of the components has a specific role which is described with details at this chapter.

Figure 28 Visualization of the utilized components of the SatisFactory Architecture at BSC-5.3

Table 35 presents the components that are common at BSC-5.3. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 35: Identified Components to be utilized at BSC-5.3

Responsible partner	
ABE	Component: Integrated DSS
	Prerequisites: Provision of all necessary data from the shop floors. Working environment and scheduling allows for all needed maintenance procedures.
	Restrictions: In case all maintenance activities cannot be performed for some reason, information is needed on how to prioritise them.
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools
	Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job
	Restrictions: The presentation tools will be visualize all and only the supported contents (images, text, icons) Prerequisites: Clear and effective messages (images, text, icons) have to be generated at runtime by external specialized components and sent to AR Tools that will present these contents in pre-designed HMIs
REGOLA	Component: AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework
	Prerequisites: Formalized (maintenance) operating procedures to correctly reconfigure plant. Any resources (images, 3d models, ...) useful to describe the procedures themselves
CERTH	Component: Plant Data Exchange Component (PDEC) Restrictions: The PDEC must have a continuous operation because pilot plants at CERTH/CPERI shop floor are on 24 hours. Prerequisites: OPC connection between the SCADA systems and the PDEC

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

6.1.1 Integrated DSS

As previously described, the iDSS interacts with other components in order to carry out a specific task. The iDSS within BSC-5.3 will receive a notification of a need for reconfiguration most probably by an Actor. The DSS Core will be triggered to interact (probably by the Incident Management Tool) with Operating Procedures, Maintenance Procedures and the Maintenance Toolkit. Thus, the system will be able to provide suggestions on the actions required, along with the information necessary, which reside in the Repository. The information will be combined in the Shop floor Feedback Engine and it will be redirected to the corresponding visualization sub-component. More details about the iDSS are presented at paragraph 4.1.3.

Table 36: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
As previously stated, the development of the sub-components of the iDSS has begun, with the main focus being up to this point in the DSS-Core, Maintenance Procedures, Incident Management Tools and Maintenance Toolkit.
Required input
For iDSS to operate in BSC-5.3, the need for reconfiguration must be identified outside of Integrated DSS and the notification must be fed to the DSS core from the operator/actor. Moreover, the analytical operating and maintenance procedures need to be made available from the shop floor involved and the related material and information to be made available at the Repository. Additionally, inferred ontologies from the Ontology Manager need to be available for inquiring.

Estimation of delivery

The first version of the iDSS with the sub-components necessary for the implementation of this specific Business Scenario is anticipated to be ready by M19. Several parts of the tool will be made gradually available from M16 and on, in order to test the information flow applicability.

6.1.2 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools

The AR SOP Creation Tool has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.4 . At the BSC-5.3, the AR SOP Creation Tool is used to provide assistance to the worker through the detailed standard operating procedures that will be created. This is a very helpful function which can help both experienced and novice employees. The whole procedure of the reconfiguration of the process of the pilot plant will be demonstrated through the AR tools and will give extra assistance to the operators and the technicians who are involved at this business scenario.

6.1.3 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job

The AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.5. At the BSC-5.3, this component is used in combination with the AR Creation Tools to provide assistance to the worker through the detailed standard operating procedures that will be created. This tool is responsible to present the created information to the workers through the AR tools.

6.1.4 AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework

The AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework has been analyzed with details at the paragraph 4.1.6. At the BSC-5.3, this component is used in combination with the AR Creation Tools and the AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job to provide assistance to the worker through the detailed standard operating procedures that will be created.

6.1.5 Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC

The Plant Data Exchange Component has been described with details at section 4.1.1 . The BSC-5.3 uses PDEC to validate the actions of the operators and the technicians during the reconfiguration of the process flow of the pilot plant.

6.2 SATISFACTORY ACTORS INVOLVED

The actors at Satisfactory are being separated at groups, different in each shop floor. Every group has one or more employees who perform the same kind of tasks inside the shop floors. An actor can be experienced, trainee or novice. Detailed analysis of the actors has been help for the purposes of the deliverable D1.2. The following table shows the groups of actors that are involved at BSC-5.3.

Table 37: List with the Satisfactory actors' groups that are involved at BSC-5.3

	Groups of actors
BSC 5.3	Floor Manager
	Electrical technician
	Process technician
	Automation technician
	Process operator
	Process supervisor

6.3 STATUS OF THE BUSINESS SCENARIO 5.3

Business Scenario 5.3 will be a guide for the process operators and the technicians in order to perform the reconfiguration of the process flow at a pilot plant inside the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. This procedure is very complex and frequently the workers are facing various difficulties. The components that have been decided to be involved in this scenario are focusing on the assistance of the workers and on how to make their actions easier and more accurate. Thus, the confidence of the workers is increasing along with their satisfaction. They are able to perform their work easier, facing fewer problems. This scenario is also used for training purposes on novice workers. The following table presents the status of all involved components at BSC-5.3.

Table 38: Gantt Diagram with the implementation of the components involved at BSC-5.3

	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20
BSC-5.3 –Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures								
Integrated DSS	Design	Set-up		Deployment				Operation
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Creation Tools	Design	Set-up		Deployment			Operation	
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools On the job	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation	
AR In-Factory Platform - AR SOP Presentation Tools in Simulated Framework	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation	
Plant Data Exchange Component - PDEC	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
GENERAL COMPONENTS								
Repository-Asset machinery,production models	Design	Set-up		Deployment				Operation
Operational platform with augmented intelligence	Design	Set-up		Deployment			Operation	
Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager	Design	Set-up		Deployment			Operation	
Suggestion for improvement platform - My Factory - Gamification - based tools	Design				Set-up	Deployment	Operation	
Suggestions for Improvement – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools	Design				Set-up	Deployment		
Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools	Design			Set-up		Deployment	Operation	
Gamification Framework – “What’s My Score” App – Gamification-based tools	Design			Set-up		Deployment	Operation	
Middleware – Device Manager	Design	Set-up		Deployment		Operation		
Middleware - Core Services	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Middleware - Event Manager	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				
Event Aggregator	Design	Set-up	Deployment	Operation				

Where the operation phase is missing from a component, this means that it is scheduled after month 20 (M20). The operation of the installed components/tools that start within the timeframe of the Table 38 will continue towards the 2nd iteration of T5.3 activities until M24

7 BSC-6.1 – RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS AND PATH OPTIMIZATION FOR WORKERS MOVEMENT ON THE SHOP FLOOR

The goal of chapter 7 is to describe the planning for implementation and the initial setup and initial usage of the available components/tools at the scenario BSC-6.1. The Business Scenario 6.1 of CERTH refers to movement at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. Two functions for this scenario have been implemented, one about recognition of incidents and one about the localization within the shop floor. Many incidents mostly minor but sometimes major with many workers involved, could happen every day in an industrial shop floor.

Goals:

- Prevent incidents by online monitoring of the status at the shop-floor
- Optimize movement at the shop floor

Objective

- Reduce incidents caused by accidental drop of objects or movement of materials through frequently used corridors concurrently by many workers
- Identify potential incidents of a worker

The purpose of this scenario is to reduce the number of this kind of incidents and to give optimal notification to workers moving inside the shop floor. This will have a positive impact to the workers' safety, which is a main aspect that SatisFactory targets.

Figure 29 Movement tracking at CERTH/CPERI's shop floor through normal camera

Figure 30 Movement tracking at CERTH/CPERI's shop floor through depth camera

Minor incidents involving workers frequently occur, causing delays and/or difficulties to complete the performed actions. Identification of such incidents and their severity, along with automatically recalling knowhow based on previously occurred incidents and providing suggested actions, would be a substantial solution to the problem. There are some areas of the shop floor that need particular attention from the workers when they are moving inside them. SatisFactory will be an assistant to the workers, trying to find optimal and safer paths for them to move and to perform their actions.

The safety of the workers is the main concept of this business scenario by providing the optimal way to perform standard procedures as well as optimal 3D movement within the shop floor.

7.1 SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS USED

For the implementation of the BSC-6.1 a set of components of the SatisFactory platform will be used in order to realize the procedures and activities of the scenarios. Figure 31 shows the subset of the components that are invoked to be used by the scenario, at least in its current form according to the feedback and collaboration achieved during task T5.3.

Figure 31: Visualization of the utilized components of the SatisFactory Architecture at BSC-6.1

Table 39 presents the components that are common at BSC-6.1. Besides the name and the technology partner responsible for the components, the restrictions and the necessary prerequisites for the proper installation/operation are described.

Table 39: Identified Components to be utilized at BSC-6.1

Responsible partner	
ISMB	Component: Smart Sensor Network - Dependable Network Infrastructure Restrictions: UWB radio connectivity can be affected by the harsh industrial environment Prerequisites: UWB anchor nodes and a gateway has to be deployed
ISMB	Component: Smart Sensor Network - UWB Localization Devices Restrictions: UWB radio connectivity can be affected by the harsh industrial environment

	Prerequisites: UWB anchor nodes and a gateway has to be deployed
CERTH	Component: Smart Sensor Network - Depth Sensor Network
	Restrictions: There should NOT be materials that would probably lead to misfunctionality of the cameras (areas with a lot glasses, mirrors, and other reflection materials) Prerequisites: There should be available (a) the architectural map (floor plan) of the area under interest, (b) TCP/IP network, (c) power supply
CERTH	Component: Smart Sensor Network - Thermal Sensor Network
	Prerequisites: There should be available (a) TCP/IP network, (b) power supply.
ISMB	Component: Context-Aware Manager - Localization Manager
	Prerequisites: Shoop floor layout is available in electronic format (general user safety information are available)
ISMB	Component: Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager
	Restrictions: If it's in scope of this UC to monitor if a worker is wearing the required safety equipment for the desired area, cameras needs to be placed in the specific positions with specific view angles. Moreover, fall detection system is in scope and active in the smart assembly areas.
CERTH	Component: Integrated DSS - Incident Management Tools
	Restrictions: It will be able to detect incidents only to the areas that are monitored by cameras (depth/thermal). The number of cameras is depended on the area under interest Prerequisites: The architectural map (floor plan) of the area under monitoring should be available, the material of the area should be appropriate (there are problems with areas with a lot glasses, mirrors, and other reflection materials)
GlassUP	Component: Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices - Glasses UI
	Restrictions: Glasses only to display alert signals to user.
ISMB	Component: Context-Aware Manager - Digital Andon
	Restrictions: at the moment visual instruction are static and preloaded. Once LinkSmart will be fully integrated, this information is suitable to be retrieved from the DSS Prerequisites: assembly instructions must be available

At the following sections details about each component and its status, along with required input and delivery timeframe is described.

7.1.1 Smart Sensor Network - Dependable Network Infrastructure

The dependable sensor network is a subset of the Smart Sensor Network (SSN) consisting of heterogeneous devices that allow the interaction between the physical world and the SatisFactory framework.

This component guarantees communication robustness and correct data delivery in the industrial harsh radio propagation environments enabling context-aware applications in SatisFactory. This infrastructure hosts the sensing and actuation applications that integrate physical-world events from the shop floor into the cyber-world following an IoT approach. In this specific scenario, it provides a robust communication for low power wireless sensors.

Table 40: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
Finalized the design at high level of the multi-radio modules and RF interfaces
Required input
Communication and application requirements related to the sensors.

Estimation of delivery

The first version of the Dependable Network Infrastructure will be deployed at CERTH/CPERI shop floor at M18.

7.1.2 Smart Sensor Network - UWB Localization Devices

The UWB Localization Devices can be of three types: tag, anchor and gateway and are used to provide location information of workers. Typically, the anchors are deployed in fixed and well know positions in the environment while the tags are worn by workers whose positions need to be estimated. In particular, each tag performs distance measurements with respect to the anchors. A localization algorithm runs on the tag that uses as input distance measurements and anchor positions. Finally, the gateway is the end-point of the localization devices; it receives localization data from tags and forwards them to the Localization Manager through the Middleware. In this specific scenario, the UWB Localization Devices provides real-time positioning data of workers enabling safety management in the shop-floor.

At the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI, at this phase, there are four anchors that are at the corners or the covered area. These anchors are shown at the next table.

Table 41: Installed anchor nodes at CERTH/CPERI shop floor for the localization manager

Along with the above hardware, there is the Ultra Wide Band (UWB) Gateway (Figure 32) and the wearable sensor (Figure 33) that will be carried by the actors and will send information about their position to the UWB gateway.

Figure 32: UWB gateway

Figure 33: wearable sensor

All the above installed hardware devices are sending data to the Localization Manager component which will be described at paragraph 7.1.5

Table 42: Information of the Status and the required input of the Localization Devices

Status
A first version of the UWB Localization Devices has been developed and the UWB GW has been integrated with the LinkSmart Middleware. At the moment, the UWB tag is a commercial module from a UWB kit because the final UWB wearable device is not ready yet.
Required input
This module requires as input coordinates and identifiers of UWB anchors and the localization update rate.

Estimation of delivery

The UWB Localization Devices will be deployed at CERTH/CPERI shop floor at M17.

7.1.3 Smart Sensor Network - Depth Sensor Network

In this scenario, it is envisaged that the depth sensor network will be used to validate each step of the repair/ restore procedure. Depth cameras are responsible for capturing the movements of the actor during the repair/ restore procedure, detect arm (hand) gestures and combined with feedback provided by the SCADA, the success of each step will be determined.

Table 43: Information of the Status and the required input of the depth sensor network

Status
The software implementation for the arm (hand) gesture recognition is already in a first draft version and simultaneously a series of actions have begun to correlate information from the SCADA while also presenting success/failure messages to the SatisFactory platform.
Required input
For accurate configuration and determination of successful or failed steps of a repair/restore procedure the Depth Sensor Network must have feedback from the SCADA system. In addition, access to shop floor and equipment topology is required, which is achieved through the CIDEM.

The following figure shows the depth sensors that have been installed at the shop floor of CERTH/CPERI. They have been functioning for retrieving test data in order to improve their behavior and results. They are in the deployment phase now, in which the results are being evaluate in order to start the operation phase with the implementation of the scenarios.

Figure 34 Depth camera installed at CERTH/CPERI floor

Estimation of delivery

The implementation of the Depth Sensor Network is part of T3.3 which is due M30. However, given the integration effort that will be required among the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager, the

Multiple-Media Manager and the Localization Manager, the Smart Sensor Network should be fully operational by M24, while the first operational version is expected to be up and running by M19.

The depth cameras are already installed in a preliminary setup at CERTH/CPERI and will be finally delivered to be tested by M19.

7.1.4 Smart Sensor Network - Thermal Sensor Network

The Thermal Sensor Network will support real-time condition monitoring of critical shop floor components (e.g. control cabinet) based on image segmentation, spatio-temporal image analysis (analysis of aggregated energy images) and template matching for abnormal pattern detection of thermal image information, supporting the operation of the incident detection engine. The aforementioned procedure will lead to reduced unscheduled down times and catastrophic failures and eventually to safer worker environments, thus increasing worker’s comfort. Using a custom-made calibration pattern, the system is able to perform 3D thermal image analysis and support virtual fencing of dangerous areas, thus further improving safety within the shop floor environment.

The following figure shows two instances of a control cabinet at CERTH/CPERI shop floor. The normal function is shown at the left instance and the function with the problem is shown at the right instance. The object inside the red cycle has increased its temperature much higher than normal and the component will understand this abnormal function. A message to the involved components is going to be produced in order to examine if this situation requires an alarm or any other action.

Figure 35 Photos of a normal and an abnormal condition of a control cabinet

Table 44: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status

As mentioned above a custom made calibration pattern has been designed and manufactured in order to provide 3D thermal image analysis in the pilot plant. The calibration method has been completed and for the next few months there will be a simultaneous effort to collect thermal image datasets from various incidents at shop floor level along with the algorithmic process for real-time condition monitoring. The implementation of the algorithms has already begun and will be validated through the datasets collected both offline and in real-time operation.

Required input

Topology information along with some technical characteristics for the physical assets (i.e. nominal operation temperature) is needed as input for the Thermal Sensor Network. Thus, information stored in CIDEM is required for the Network's operation.

Estimation of delivery

Information provided from the Thermal Sensor Network is needed for the Gesture & Content Recognition Manager which is developed in T3.3 and is expected to be completed by M30. Therefore, the final version of the Network should be completed earlier on M26, while the first operational version is expected to be up and running by M20, after the complete collection of the needed datasets.

7.1.5 Context-Aware Manager - Localization Manager

The Localization Manager provides as output the location of workers given as input the identifier of the associated UWB device. In this specific scenario, the Localization Manager provides the location of the worker who has to repair the malfunction. This information along with the location of the malfunction (both displayed on a map) allows the worker to take the right direction to reach the malfunction in the shortest possible time. In addition, given as input the location of the malfunction, the Localization Manager can find the closest worker with the appropriate skill.

Table 45: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
A first version of the Localization Manager including geo-fencing logic has been developed and integrated with the LinkSmart middleware.
Required input
This module requires as input localization data from the UWB devices through the event manager of the middleware.

Estimation of delivery

The first version of the Localization Manager will be deployed at the CERTH/CPERI shop-floor at M17.

Both software and hardware have been installed at CERTH/CPERI premises for this component so far. The hardware that is co-operating with the Localization Manager has been described at the paragraph 7.1.2. The user interface that is shown at next two figures receives the information from the hardware and presents them to the user. Figure 36 shows a worker who is moving inside a permitted area. The forbidden zone has green color which means that there aren't any workers inside it.

Figure 36: The worker is moving to a permitted area

Figure 37 shows an instance where a worker has entered the forbidden zone. The area has become red at the interface and a message is displayed at the UI. The same message, along with more details, is being sent to the middleware in order to be transmitted to any of the other components of the SatisFactory platform needs to use this information.

Figure 37: The worker has entered a forbidden area

7.1.6 Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager

The Gesture & Content Recognition Manager component has been described with details at the paragraph 5.1.6. At the BSC-6.1 will also contribute for assisting workers by demonstrating some actions or schematics regarding the shop floor area.

7.1.7 Integrated DSS - Incident Management Tools

The Incident Management Tools monitor behavior of sensors placed on reactors of a factory’s system, providing primarily an on-time warning of a possible abnormal situation, and secondly a prediction of how the reactor is going to behave after at least one minute time interval, leading to a timely notification of a possible upcoming abnormal behavior which may lead to an incident. By modeling the overall system’s behavior both on normal and abnormal situations through an amount of historical data, formed in time-series, real-time values will be able to be categorized either in normal state or in abnormal state according to a probability value. The system will also provide appropriate warnings and notifications for the reactor’s operators.

Table 46: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
Extended research has been done on methods that could model behavior of factory’s systems and methods regarding incident detection and early warning notification. The most appropriate ones have been implemented and applied on a pilot plant unit at CETH/CPERI. The methods that gave interesting results are going to be integrated on the application in order to visualize behavior and make it easier to extract knowledge.
Required input
The application is reading the essential data from CIDEM. Data such as the number of systems existing in the factory, the number of units each system has and the number of sensors placed on each unit, the topology of each system/sensor, real-time and historical measurements are all provided through REST services from CIDEM.

Estimation of delivery

The Incident Management Tools is included in the components developed in T3.3 and thus it is due M30. The first version is almost completed and will be put into real-time testing by the end of M19 while the final version version is expected to be available by M29.

7.1.8 Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI

The Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices component is also being used at BSC-5.1 and BSC-5.2 and it has been analyzed at paragraph 4.1.7. The worker will wear the smart glasses and he/she will be able to receive useful information about the actions that have to be done.

7.1.9 Context-Aware Manager - Digital Andon Component

The Digital Andon component is a component that acts as an enabler in order to facilitate performing specific operations through the visual representation of status information.

Figure 38: A screen shot of the Digital Andon function

The first iteration of the Digital Andon will be deployed in the smart assembly stations and directly connected to the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager. The latter is a headless component that interacts directly with the Digital Andon system. The goal is to provide the worker useful information while performing the assembly task. While browsing through the information is a direct responsibility of the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager component, the Digital Andon is in charge of displaying gesture-related information and dispatch notifications about the progress status.

Table 47: Information of the Status and the required input of the component

Status
The Digital Andon has been tested with other components such as the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager and the Toolkit for re-adaptation. It is still required from end-users to finalize assembly instructions.
Required input
Gestures from the Gestures & Content Recognition Manager component, assembly instructions to be displayed.

Estimation of delivery

At the current development status the Digital Andon is ready to be deployed in its first iteration (M18). Further refinement and full integration with Middleware will be required after the pre-pilot operation which will be help until M20.

7.2 *SATISFACTORY ACTORS INVOLVED*

The actors at SatisFactory are being separated at groups, different in each shop floor. Every group has one or more employees who perform the same kind of tasks inside the shop floors. An actor can be experienced, trainee or novice. Detailed analysis of the actors has been help for the purposes of the deliverable D1.2. The following table shows the groups of actors that are involved at BSC-6.1.

Table 48: List with the SatisFactory actors' groups that are involved at BSC-6.1

	Groups of actors
BSC 6.1	Maintenance manager
	Maintenance supervisor
	Process operator
	Process technician

7.3 *STATUS OF THE BUSINESS SCENARIO 6.1*

Business Scenario 6.1 will focus at the safety of the workers at the shop floor are. Workers feel safer in the areas that the tools operate and they are going to perform their daily actions with more confidence. The satisfaction regarding their work will increase and so will their performance. The following table presents the status of all involved components at BSC-6.1.

Table 49: Gantt Diagram with the implementation of the components involved at BSC-6.1

	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20		
BSC-6.1 –Recognition of accidents and path optimization for workers movement on the shop floor										
Smart Sensor Network - Dependable Network Infrastructure	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Smart Sensor Network - UWB Localization Devices	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Smart Sensor Network - Depth Sensor Network	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Smart Sensor Network - Thermal Sensor Network	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Context-Aware Manager - Localization Manager	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Context-Aware Manager - Gesture & Content Recognition Manager	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Integrated DSS - Incident Management Tools	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Multi modal & Augmented HMIs and AR devices – Glasses UI	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Context-Aware Manager - Digital Andon Component	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
GENERAL COMPONENTS										
Repository-Asset machinery, production models	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Operational platform with augmented intelligence	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Semantic Context Manager - Ontology Manager	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Suggestion for improvement platform - My Factory - Gamification - based tools	Design				Set-up		Deployment		Operation	
Suggestions for Improvement – “My Factory Management” – Gamification-based tools	Design				Set-up		Deployment			
Gamification Framework – Gamification-based tools	Design				Set-up		Deployment		Operation	
Gamification Framework – “What’s My Score” App – Gamification-based tools	Design				Set-up		Deployment		Operation	
Middleware – Device Manager	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Middleware - Core Services	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Middleware - Event Manager	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			
Event Aggregator	Design		Set-up		Deployment		Operation			

Where the operation phase is missing from a component, this means that it is scheduled after month 20 (M20). The operation of the installed components/tools that start within the timeframe of the Table 49 will continue towards the 2nd iteration of T5.3 activities until M24.

8 CONCLUSIONS - RESULTS FROM THE IMPLEMENTATION PLANNING

The implementation phase of SatisFactory focuses on the deployment of the solution to the operating environment of the participating shop floors. The activities that are documented at deliverable D5.2 are related to CETH/CPERI shop floor where the business scenarios that are derived by actor's needs and requirements are implemented. Using a formal stage-based approach the demonstration of the usage of the SatisFactory platform is targeted. The 1st version of D5.3, which is the current document is about planning for implementation and describes the status of all the necessary components and tools and how and when they are or will be deployed at the shop floor of CETH/CPERI.

One of the objectives of the present deliverable was to establish a common ground on which the WP5 tasks (T5.2 and T5.5), and the connected technical WPs (WP2 to WP4), will verify their development towards the demonstration to the full-scale industrial shop floors (T5.4). This work followed the business scenario driven approach, starting with the potential restrictions, any obstacles and the determination of the prerequisites for each component or group of components and identification of the participating actors. Each scenario demonstrates different aspects of the delivered tools. The initial implementation-planning phase is the basis for the demonstration of SatisFactory platform. Overall at D5.3 a preliminary schedule was prepared in order to perform the test work for all SatisFactory components/tools and prototype platform and to be tested as described. The schedule is developed in conjunction with the development operations from the WP2, WP3 and WP4 that will facilitate proper evaluation and potential reconfiguration.

The findings from the implementation at small-scale will be a reference point for the up-scaled demonstrations and will give the opportunity to the technology providing partners to handle any technical issues that will be revealed by the activities of task T5.3. Also, as a preliminary engagement of the CETH/CPERI actors was performed, their feedback will be carefully evaluated, as the tools will be gradually delivered and will be used at the actual working environment.

ANNEX 1 – DETAILED STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES FOR INDICATIVE BSC

BSC-5.1 - Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction

Step No	Basic Steps	Pictures	Additional Info
1.	The operator or the SCADA system identifies a malfunction		Data from SCADA Current Value: TE82.F_CV Set Point: TIC82A.F_TV1 Output: TY82A.F_CV
2.	The operator declares the new job at the iDSS		
3.	The technician receives the ticket for the new job and moves to the point that the system has identified		
4.	The technician opens the door of the electrical enclosure		

<p>5.</p>	<p>The AR tool (e.g. tablet) displays the appropriate electrical drawings to the technician</p>		
<p>6.</p>	<p>The AR tool locates the involved fuse, screw terminals and solid state relay and magnifies on them at the schematics</p>		
<p>7.</p>	<p>If there is a hihi alarm the technician checks the solid state relay. If not go to step 14</p>		<p>BSC51-step7 SSR_CHECK_OK</p> <p>BSC51-step7 SSR_CHECK_NOT_OK</p>
<p>8.</p>	<p>After that the technician removes the appropriate fuse</p>		
<p>9.</p>	<p>The operator must set manual 0 at the output of the controller at the SCADA system</p>		

10.	The technician removes the wires of the relay and replaces it		BSC51-step10 REPLACE_SSR
11.	The technician connects back the fuse		
12.	The operator starts the auto function of the controller		
13.	The operator gives feedback whether the problem has been solved or not		
14.	If there is a lolo alarm the technician removes the appropriate fuse and checks it with the multimeter		BSC51-step14 CHECK_FUSE
15.	The operator must set manual 0 at the output of the controller at the SCADA system		

16.	If the fuse is burned out, the technician replaces it		BSC51-step16 INSTALL_FUSE
17.	The technician removes the wires of the resistor from the terminals		
18.	The technician measures the resistor with the multimeter		BSC51-step18 CHECK_RESISTOR
19.	If the resistor is burned out. The AR tool indicates where the resistor is located		
20.	The technician replaces it		
21.	If not he connects back the fuse and the resistor wires		
22.	The technician takes a snapshot of the area where the equipment is placed and the AR tool displays a list with all the parts that exist at		

	that point (from the identified assets as described at P&ID)		
23.	The technician choses the equipment that was involved along with the actions taken and the results		
24.	The AR tool sends feedback to the iDSS for the specific job (which was declared at step 2)		

BSC-5.3 - Reconfiguration of process flow and actions for flexible redesign of production procedures

Step No	Basic Steps	Pictures
1.	Identify the MFC that need to be replaced (Methane -> Ethane, FT/FV-21C)	
2.	The volumetric flow rate range required at the previous experiment is 0-5000 cc/min, while the at next experiment is 0-3000 cc/min, thus another MFC, calibrated for Ethane, should be installed.	
3.	Calibrate the new MFC according to the gas (ethane) and the flow rate (0-3000 cc/min) to be used (if needed)	
4.	Uninstall the previous MFC and install the new MFC	
5.	Identify the GB that need to be replaced (Methane -> Ethane)	
6.	Make sure that the valve of the GB is closed	

7.	Remove the previously used GB (methane)	
8.	Install the new GB (ethane)	
9.	Update the ranges of the installed MFC in the HMI Database. The new MFC's volumetric flow rate range is 0-3000 cc/min.	
10.	Update the upper and lower boundaries of alarms in the HMI Database. Volumetric flowrate (0-3000 cc/min), pressure (0-10 barg) and temperature (0-300 °C) boundaries need to be updated.	
11.	Change the method that is used in the chromatograph so that the new outlet stream's composition can be identified. The previous method is "SYNGAS22.M" while the new one to be used is "SYNEX21.M"	
12.	After everything (MFC & GB) have been installed in the pilot plant a pressure test needs to be performed in order to check for possible leaks before operating the unit.	
13.	In order to perform a pressure loss test Valves HV-81 (or HV-80) and 6HV-81 needs to be (manually) closed.	
14.	Subsequently nitrogen is introduced into the system by setting the appropriate MFC's (FC-21C) volumetric flow rate at 200 cc/min.	

15.	When the pressure at PI-81 reaches 10 bar (depending on the reaction's conditions), the flow rate is set to 0 cc/min and Valve XV-21C is closed.	
16.	The pressure loss test is performed overnight, pressurizing by mean of Valve XV-21C and HV-81. If loss of pressure exceeds 5% overnight, or the leaking flow exceeds 2cc/min, then check for leaks with Helium Leak Detector (HLD)	
17.	If loss of pressure exceeds 5% overnight, or the leaking flow exceeds 2cc/min, then check for leaks with Helium Leak Detector (HLD)	